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Particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces: physico-chemical foundations

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Abstract

Particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces are ubiquitous in academia and industry, which has fostered extensive research efforts trying to disentangle the physico-chemical bases underlying the trapping of particles to fluid/fluid interfaces as well as the properties of the obtained layers. The understanding of such aspects is essential for exploiting the ability of particles on the stabilization of fluid/fluid interface for the fabrication of novel interface-dominated devices, ranging from traditional Pickering emulsions to more advanced reconfigurable devices. This review tries to provide a general perspective of the physico-chemical aspects associated with the stabilization of interfaces by colloidal particles, mainly chemical isotropic spherical colloids. Furthermore, some aspects related to the exploitation of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces on the stabilization of emulsions and foams will be also highlighted. It is expected that this review can be used for researchers and technologists as an initial approach to the study of particle-laden fluid layers.

Keywords: fluid/fluid interfaces, particles, colloids, interface-dominated materials

1. Introduction

The self-assembly of colloidal particles differing in chemistry, shape and size (ranging from a few nanometres to several micrometres) at fluid/fluid interfaces presents currently a very important impact in different technological fields [1]. This can be easily understood considering the multiple options offered by particle-laden interfaces for the fabrication of interface-dominated materials, i.e. materials with a total interfacial area much larger than the area of their container [2]. Thus, the accumulation of colloidal particles at the region separating two fluid phases leads to distinctive properties to the interfaces, which appears very different to that what are found for the corresponding 3D counterparts.

Furthermore, fluid/fluid interfaces open many opportunities for modulating the assembly of particles and for the chemical modification of particles [3, 4]. This has allowed its exploitation to support unique application and the fabrication of novel materials. Among such applications are included the stabilization of emulsions (Pickering emulsions and bicontinuous jammed emulsion gels, i.e. the so-called bijels), foams, liquid marbles and colloidosomes; the production of nanoporous membranes for filtration or encapsulation [5-10], and the fabrication of responsive functional materials with a broad range of electrical, optical, or magnetic properties [11-13]. Furthermore, the understanding of the physico-chemistry of particle-laden interfaces may be also important for elucidating some fundamental aspects related to the

impact of pollutants on the performance of the alveolar lining films, which is a very important problem in the modern society [14-16].

The widespread of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces in science and technology has stimulated an extensive research activity trying to shed light on some of the most fundamental aspects underlying the physico-chemical behavior of these systems [17]. This is very important because particles present some distinctive features in relation to molecular surfactants which modulate their behavior at fluid interfaces [17, 18]: (i) particles are in most cases chemically isotropic objects (Janus particles are an exception); (ii) particles do not aggregate to form micelles in bulk phases, and (iii) particles cannot undergo reorientation, reconfiguration or bending process upon trapping at the fluid/fluid interface (a certain degree of reconfiguration can appear when soft colloids, such as microgels, are concerned). These aspects are essential for defining the properties of particles trapped at fluid/fluid interfaces [1, 19].

The study of the behavior of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces is generally less straightforward than that of surfactant-laden interfaces. This may be easily understood considering the many variables that must be considered, e.g. chemical nature and anisotropy, size, shape, roughness and/or wettability. This plays a very central role on the interfacial trapping, and in particular on the energetic landscape of the adsorption of particles at a given fluid/fluid interface [1, 19, 20]. Therefore, the exploitation of the rich behavior of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces for the design and fabrication of devices makes it necessary a closer look to the parameters that control the interfacial assembly, the structure and dynamics of the particles at the interface, the properties that limit the assembly, and the rate of particle exchange.

This topical review is to provide an overview of the most relevant aspects of the current knowledge on interfacial systems composed for colloidal particles. The first part will present a discussion of some of the main aspects related to the behavior of particles attached to fluid/fluid interfaces, including an overview of the energetic landscape governing the adsorption processes, interparticle interactions, and interfacial activity. Next, some of the most relevant aspects governing the response of particle-laden systems against stresses will be discussed. The last part of this topical review will present a brief discussion on the avenues opened by particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces for the stabilization of a particular family of interface-dominated materials with potential technological impact, the so-called dispersed systems (foams and emulsions).

2. Defining the trapping of particles at fluid/fluid interfaces: the contact angle

One of the most critical issues related to the self-assembly of colloidal particles at fluid/fluid interfaces is related to the energetic balance associated with particle trapping at the interfacial region. This is guided by a very different energetic landscape to that driving the segregation of molecular surfactants to fluid/fluid interfaces.

Molecular surfactants are chemically anisotropic molecules, with two regions with a well-differentiated affinity for phases having different polarities. This chemical anisotropy plays a critical role on the attachment of surfactant molecules to the fluid interface due to the enthalpic penalty associated with the fact that one of the surfactant parts is in a “wrong” phase, i.e. a phase with very different polarity to that of the considered part of the surfactant molecules. Thus, the favorable enthalpic contribution associated with the contact of the surfactant parts with the correct phase counterbalance the entropic penalty associated with the restriction of the degrees of freedom of the surfactant, and as matter of fact the average free energy of the system is reduced. However, the above situation is not possible in most colloidal particles and the particle trapping is guided by a different mechanism, which is controlled by the particle wettability. It should be noted that Janus particles may be considered an exception to chemical anisotropy on colloidal particles. Nevertheless, their importance and particularities place the detailed discussion of Janus particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces far from the scope of this review. For further details on Janus particles at fluid/fluid interfaces, the recent review by Correia et al. [21] is recommended.

The attachment of a colloidal particle to a fluid/fluid interface occurs when the gravitational forces are overcome due to the action of the interfacial tension forces [22]. The balance between both type of forces can be evaluated in terms of the Bond number

$$Bo = \frac{(\rho_p - \rho_f) g 2R}{\gamma}, \quad (1)$$

where ρ_p and ρ_f correspond to the densities of the particle and the fluid, respectively; g is the acceleration due to the gravity; R is the particle radius, and γ the interfacial tension. For particles with size below 10 micrometers, $Bo \ll 1$ and interfacial tension forces are the dominant contribution, which makes the attachment of the particles to the fluid/fluid interface possible. Thus, assuming the simplest case of a spherical particle, initially immersed in one of the fluid phases, which diffuse vertically to the interfacial region, it may be expected that once the particle enters in contact with the interface, the particle starts to be partially wetted by the two fluid phases. Such process drives a minimization of the unfavorable fluid/fluid interaction as result of the reduction of the contact area between the two fluids, i.e. the penetration

of the particle into the fluid/fluid interface creates a “hole” [18]. Thus, the particle trapping results in a favorable contribution to the stabilization of the interface which emerges from the reduction of the mean interfacial energy. This can be defined as follows

$$E_0 = A_{P1}\gamma_{P1} + A_{P2}\gamma_{P2} - A_{12}\gamma_{12}, \quad (2)$$

with A_{P1} and A_{P2} being the contact area between particles and the two fluid phases; γ_{P1} and γ_{P2} the interfacial tensions between the solid particles and the two fluid phases; A_{12} the contact area between both fluid phases and γ_{12} the interfacial tension of the fluid/fluid interface. On the other side, it is possible to define the energy of particle whose center located at an arbitrary distance z of the interface as [23, 24]

$$E(z) = \pi R^2 \gamma_{12} \left[\left(\frac{z}{R} \right)^2 + 2 \left(\frac{\gamma_{P2} - \gamma_{P1}}{\gamma_{12}} \right) \left(\frac{z}{R} \right) + 2 \left(\frac{\gamma_{P2} + \gamma_{P1}}{\gamma_{12}} \right) - 1 \right], \quad (2)$$

with R being the particle radius. Figure 1 shows the energy of a particle at function of its position in relation to the interface, with $z=1$ indicating the fluid 1, $z=0$ the interface and $z=-1$ the fluid 2.

Figure 1. Free energy of adsorption for a particle ($R=50$ nm) in relation to its position with a hexadecane/water interface. The interfacial tensions are $\gamma_{12}= 53.5$ mN/m, $\gamma_{P1}= 28.5$ mN/m and $\gamma_{P2}= 14.2$ mN/m. Notice that $z=1$ indicates the fluid 1, $z=0$ the interface and $z=-1$ the fluid 2, and z^{\min} defines the equilibrium position. Adapted from Ballard et al. [24], Copyright (2019), with permission from The Royal Society of Chemistry.

The equilibrium position of the particle in relation to the interface can be defined assuming mechanical equilibrium, i.e. $\partial E / \partial z = 0$, as

$$z^{\min} = \frac{\gamma_{P1} - \gamma_{P2}}{\gamma_{12}} R, \quad (3)$$

and hence the change of energy associated with the transference of a particle from a fluid phase to its equilibrium position will read as

$$\Delta E_p = -\frac{\pi R^2}{\gamma_{12}} \left[\gamma_{12} - (\gamma_{P1} - \gamma_{P2}) \right]^2. \quad (4)$$

Assuming that the equilibrium position of the particle is placed at the fluid/fluid, i.e. there is equilibrium between the forces acting in the contact line or the Young's law is fulfilled, it is possible to introduce the contact angle θ of the particles with the two fluid phases in Equation (2) (see Figure 2) [25, 26]

$$0 = \gamma_{P1} - \gamma_{P2} - \gamma_{12} \cos \theta, \quad (5)$$

that can be reordered as follows

$$\cos \theta = \frac{\gamma_{P1} - \gamma_{P2}}{\gamma_{12}}, \quad (6)$$

The contact angle is a parameter related to the relative wettability of the particles for the involved fluid phases, and defines the equilibrium position of particles trapped at the fluid interface, and hence the degree of reduction of the contact area between both fluids, i.e. the size of the “hole” [18, 24].

Figure 2. Idealized picture of the position of a particle trapped on an arbitrary fluid/fluid interface. θ and R represent the contact angle or relative wettability of the particle by the interface and particle radius, respectively; γ_{P1} and γ_{P2} are the interfacial tensions between the solid particles and the two fluid phases, and γ_{12} the interfacial tensions corresponding to the fluid/fluid interface.

An oversimplified perspective provides a definition of the contact angle for particle-laden interfaces in analogy with the hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB) parameter of molecular surfactants, evaluating the preferential partition of the particles between the two fluid phases [17, 27]. This is the result of an asymmetric distribution of the interactions

through the fluid phases [28, 29]. Hence, it is possible to define two boundary situations for the wetting of colloidal particles at the fluid/fluid interface: $\theta \rightarrow 0^\circ$ and $\theta \rightarrow 180^\circ$. These limits are associated with the preferential dispersion of the particles in one of the fluid phases, and hence a negligible adsorption of the particles at the fluid/fluid interface may be expected. This makes clear that partial wetting is essential for the adsorption of colloidal particles at fluid/fluid interfaces. Therefore, assuming an interface between two fluids with very different dielectric constants, e.g. water and an alkane, it is possible to consider that particles are hydrophilic when $\theta < 90^\circ$, whereas particles will be hydrophobic for $\theta > 90^\circ$. Figure 3 presents a idealized picture of the preferential distribution of colloidal particles between two fluid phases as a function of their contact angle. It should be stressed that the adhesion of particles to the fluid/fluid interface is closely correlated to the contact angle, and consequently this parameter may affect to the potential applications of particle-laden interface due to its influence in different physico-chemical aspects of the particle-laden interface, e.g. response of the interface against a mechanical perturbation, values of the friction coefficient on microrheology experiments or assymetric distribution of interactions between particles at the interface, which modifies their ability for the interfacial stabilization [29-35].

Figure 3. Sketch of the position of a colloidal particle at a fluid/fluid interface depending on its contact angle.

The importance of the contact angle is clear because it defines the change of energy associated with the attachment of colloidal particles to the fluid interface, which is related to the difference between the energy of particles in bulk and at the fluid interface. This energy change can be defined for spherical particles, with a size small enough to neglect the gravity effect, as follows

$$\Delta E_p = -\pi R^2 \gamma_{12} (1 \pm \cos \theta)^2, \quad (7)$$

where R corresponds to the particle radius and the \pm signs accounts for the position of the particles in relation to the plane defined for the interface. Thus, for hydrophobic

particles which present their centers above the interfacial plane the equation should read with (+), whereas the sign (-) is used for hydrophilic particles which are placed at the interface with their centers below the interfacial plane. Equation (5) can be considered a rather simple but effective model providing a suitable description of the adsorption of a colloidal particle from a fluid phase to the interface, depending on three measurable parameters: the particle radius R , its wettability, accounted by the contact angle θ , and the fluid/fluid interfacial tension γ_{12} .

The above discussion evidenced the importance of the contact angle on the energetic landscape associated with the adsorption of colloidal particles to a fluid interface. However, Equation (5) also suggests that the energetic landscape may be a matter of size. This is clear from the plots in Figure 4 where the predicted contact angle dependences of the change of the energy associated with the attachment of colloidal particles to an arbitrary fluid/fluid interface with $\gamma_{12} = 50$ mN/m are shown for colloidal particles of 10 nm and 1 μ m.

Figure 4. Contact angle dependences of the attachment energy for colloidal particles with $R = 1 \mu\text{m}$ (a) and $R = 10 \text{ nm}$ (b) at a fluid/fluid interface with $\gamma_{12} = 50$ mN/m. Note the differences on the energy scales.

The energetic landscape for the attachment of particles to fluid/fluid interface obtained from the analysis of the contact angle dependences of the energy change associated with the adsorption process shows that the trapping process overcomes, in most of the cases, several times the thermal energy $k_B T$, with k_B and T being the Boltzmann constant and the absolute temperature, respectively [3], and as a matter of fact it should be considered almost irreversible. Nevertheless, any physical reliable analysis of the energetic landscape of the adsorption of particles, and its reversibility requires to

consider up to 3 different parameter: (i) contact angle θ ; (ii) particle size R , and (iii) fluid/fluid interfacial tension γ_{12} . The consideration of such parameters evidences that the trapping of particles in the micrometer range at fluid/fluid interfaces may be considered as an almost irreversible process, with the change of energy associated with such process being in the range $10^6 k_B T - 10^7 k_B T$. It should be noted that the existence of an irreversible adsorption does not indicate that colloidal particles remain trapped in fixed position within the 2D fluid layer, and the particles can freely diffuse within the fluid/fluid interface [36]. Furthermore, the thermal and capillary deformations of the interface result also in continuous fluctuations of the particle position in relation to the interfacial plane [37, 38]. On the other side, the situation is less straightforward for nanosized particles and the reversibility/irreversibility of their trapping at the fluid/fluid interface becomes a size-dependent issue, which makes necessary to consider the above mentioned three parameters. This leads to a situation in which for particles with sizes below 10 nm, the adsorption process may involve an adsorption-desorption equilibria similar to that what happens for conventional molecular surfactants [39, 40]. Thus, for nanoparticles, their weak interfacial segregation and the similarity of the values of their interfacial energy and the thermal energy may cause spatial fluctuations of the particles at the interface [41]. This is clearer from a simple analysis of the energetic balance associated with the adsorption of a single nanoparticle to the fluid/fluid interface. Therefore, assuming that the ability of particles for remaining trapped at the interface arises from a minimization of the free energy, and taking into account that there is an entropic penalty associated with the adsorption of particles at the interface (around k_B), the irreversible attachment requires a negative value for ΔE_p . Therefore, if the Equation (4) is used with the values reported in reference [41] for nanoparticles with 2.8 nm of radius at a fluid/fluid interface with $\gamma_{p1}=40$ mN/m, $\gamma_{p2}=10$ mN/m and $\gamma_{12}=35.7$ mN/m, ΔE_p is found to assume a value about $-5k_B T$. The significant differences between the trapping energies for micro- and nanoparticles arise from the R^2 -dependence of ΔE_p . Thus, it can be expected that thermal energy can induce the displacement of the smallest particles from the interface. It should be noted that the weakness of the trapping of nanoparticles at the interface results in their thermal-activated escape from the interface, with the residence time being significantly increased with the size increase. This provides a justification to the facilitated replacement of small nanoparticles from the interface upon the adsorption of biggest one [41]. It is worth mentioning that the role of the reversibility and irreversibility of the trapping of particles at fluid/fluid interfaces plays a main role on the control of their organization at the interface and the layer response to external mechanical stresses, e.g. collision between droplets in emulsions. This may be understood

considering its role on the modification of the inter-particle interactions at the interface [37].

The above discussion has provided clear evidences of the important role of the particle wettability on their adsorption at fluid/fluid interfaces, governing even the distribution of interactions across the interface, and hence the interfacial morphology of the adsorbed layer [37, 42]. These aspects may be tuned by modifying the particle wettability as shown Figure 5, and hence their trapping to the fluid/fluid interface.

Figure 5. Idealized picture of the possible impact of the particle wettability on their organization at the fluid/fluid interface. Reprinted from Garbin et al. [43], Copyright (2012), with permission from Elsevier.

There are currently available several physical and chemical methods enabling the modification of the wetting properties of particles for fluid/fluid interfaces. The former approach relies on the capping of the particles by using surfactants, polymers or even low molecular weight molecules, such as alcohols, that can interact with the particle surface through non-covalent interactions, e.g. hydrogen bonds, electrostatic or van der Waals one [44-55]. On the other side, the chemical modification of particle surface relies on the irreversible attachment of capping-ligands using covalent-like bonding, e.g. thiols on gold surfaces or silanes on silicon dioxide one [56, 57]. The modification of the wettability of silica particles by silanization can result in 2-fold increase of the value of θ with a decrease of the number of dissociated silanol groups on the particle surface from 34% to 20% [58]. Similar effects were found by the chemical modification of polystyrene latex particles by grafting poly(glycerol-monomethacrylate) chains on their surface. The increase of the length of the grafted chains leads to an enhancement of the hydrophilicity of the particles, resulting in a decrease of the contact angle of particles at water/non-polar fluid interfaces (both air/water and *n*-dodecane/water) [59]. Maestro et al. [53] exploited the interaction between two different cationic surfactants, belonging to the family of the alkyltrimethylammonium bromides (hexadecyl-trimethylammonium bromide, CTAB and dodecyl-trimethylammonium bromide, DTAB), for modifying the wettability of silica nanoparticles through non-covalent interactions. Their results evidenced that the particle modification appears governed by a complex balance of interactions involving hydrophobic and electrostatic one.

This makes it possible to tune almost at will the contact angle of the particles by changing the concentration of added surfactant, with the maximum value of the particle contact angle (maximum degree of hydrophobization) being reached when the concentration of surfactant is high enough to take the particles to the isoelectric point (neutralization). Further increases of the surfactant concentration beyond the isoelectric point results in a rehydrophilization of the particles, thus decreasing the contact angle. Similar behaviour was found by Binks et al. [60] by mixing silica particles and a surfactant having two tails (didecyldimethylammonium bromide). It should be stressed that the control of the particle wettability by fluid/fluid interfaces has received a big interest in recent years, which has driven important research efforts on the design of new particles with asymmetrical wettability, including Janus particles and patchy colloids [21, 61-65].

2.2 Line tension and roughness: neglected contributions to particle wettability

The above framework does not provide under some specific condition a suitable description of the particle trapping at the fluid/fluid interface. This can be ascribed to the emergence of additional contributions associated with the particle roughness and/or the line tension [66]. The latter arises from the imbalance of the intermolecular forces within the three phase contact line. The sign and magnitude of line tension depends on the interfacial potential emerging from the intermolecular interactions appearing in the surrounding of the contact line [67]. The contribution of the line tension can be either positive or negative, with a magnitude in the range 1-100 pN [24, 68].

The contribution of the line tension τ to the attachment of a particle to the fluid/fluid interface may be accounted by modifying the Young's equation according to the expression proposed by Bresme and Quirke [69-71], which assumes that interfacial tensions and line tensions depend on the contact angle

$$\frac{\gamma_{P1} - \gamma_{P2}}{\cos \theta} - \gamma_{12} = -\frac{\tau}{R \sin \theta}, \quad (8)$$

which results in a energy variation for the trapping of a particle at the fluid/fluid interface given as

$$\Delta E_p = \gamma_{12} \cos \theta_\infty 2\pi R^2 (1 - \cos \theta) + 2\tau \pi R \sin \theta - \pi R^2 \gamma_{12} \cos^2 \theta, \quad (9)$$

with θ_∞ indicating the macroscopic contact angle provided by the Young's equation (Equation (6)). Therefore, assuming mechanical and thermal equilibrium of the particle-laden

fluid/fluid interface, i.e. $(\partial \Delta E_p / \partial \theta)_T = 0$, it is possible to define the true contact angle as follows

$$\cos \theta = \cos \theta_\infty \left[1 - \frac{\tau}{R \gamma_{12}} \right]^{-1}. \quad (10)$$

For intermediate wetting conditions, i.e. $\theta \rightarrow 90^\circ$, the role of the line tension is negligible, and Equation (6) and Equation (10) provide similar values of the contact angle. This is explained considering that the line tension is almost perpendicular to the fluid/fluid interface, and hence the tangential component of τ is very small and does not impact on the flotation height of the particle at the fluid/fluid interface [18, 24]. However, for particles with contact angles different from 90° , the tangential component of the line tension is relatively high, with the maximum contribution of the line tension to the particle wetting being expected for $\theta \rightarrow 0^\circ$ and $\theta \rightarrow 180^\circ$ [72]. This can result in positive values of the free energy change associated with the particle attachment to the fluid/fluid interface or the emergence of an activation barrier for the particle adsorption even for negative changes on the free energy, with the latter being associated with a metastable or unstable condition. Thus, the line tension contribution results in significant differences between the contact angles values obtained from Equation (6) and Equation (10). However, it should be stressed that the role of the line tension only plays an important role for particles below 20 nm [28, 73-76].

It is worth mentioning that the line tension increases its impact with the deviation of the particle shape from the spherical one and the increase of the particle roughness because it increases the contribution of the contact line length in relation to the particle volume [73].

The roughness and porosity may also influence decisively to the wetting properties of colloidal particles by fluid/fluid interfaces, and in particular for the smallest particles [44, 52]. This may be understood considering that an increase of the roughness and porosity of the particles may result in an increase of the particle contact angle, which can be accounted on the bases of the Cassie-Baxter model, especially for particles with a high roughness [77]. Thus, the emergence of asymmetric wetting conditions along the contact line drives to different pinning-depinning phenomena of the particles at the interface. Furthermore, the roughness and porosity can influence the adsorption of surface-active modifiers onto the particles. Nonomura and Komura [77] showed using theoretical calculations that the wetting of particles may be governed by an intricate balance between different parameters: (i) interfacial tensions between particles and fluid phases; (ii) particle sizes, and (iii) fraction of surface area of the particle that is in contact with the fluid/phase. Despite its clear importance of the trapping of

particles at fluid/fluid interfaces, the impact of the roughness and the porosity in the wetting properties of particles at fluid/fluid interface has not been systemically addressed yet.

2.3 Experimental evaluation of the contact angle of particles trapped at fluid/fluid interfaces

The above discussion has shown the importance of the contact angle on the understanding of the attachment of particles to fluid/fluid interfaces. However, the determination of such parameter is challenging [78-80], and there is no a standard approach enabling the determination of the contact angle of particles, independently of their dimensions, shape and morphology. Currently, the most common methods providing information about the contact angle of particles trapped at fluid/fluid interfaces can be classified in three different groups: indirect measurements, direct measurements of multiple particles, and direct measurements of single particles [81]. Hereafter, a brief introduction to some of the most extended techniques for the determination of the contact angle of particles at fluid/fluid interfaces will be presented. It should be noted that an exhaustive analysis of the different techniques used for evaluating the contact angle of particle trapped at fluid/fluid interfaces appears out of the scope of this articles, and the reading of references [20, 82-84] is highly recommended for a more complete perspective.

2.3.1 Indirect methods. The indirect methods rely on the evaluation of an interfacial property associated with the contact angle. This property can be related through a theory with the contact angle, providing an average value of the contact angle for all the particles. It should be stressed that these methodologies do not give access to a direct measurement of the contact angle or particle position.

A very common indirect approach for evaluating the contact angle of particles is to assume that the contact angle for a particle trapped at the fluid/fluid interface is the same of a droplet of liquid on the surface of a flat substrate with the same composition. This allows evaluating the contact angle by analysing the profile of the deposited droplet using a drop shape tensiometer [85]. However, this approach fails in most of the cases because it neglects the role of the curvature, roughness and line tension on the contact angle of particles at fluid/fluid interfaces.

Another alternative is the evaluation of the interfacial pressure-area (Π - A) isotherms of the particle-laden interfaces. This approach can give information about the contact angle following two different approaches: (i) analysis of the area exclusion effects, and (ii) evaluation of the collapse pressure. The former approach relies on the evaluation of the area shifts of the Π - A isotherm of an insoluble surfactant due to the addition of colloidal particles. This methodology assumes that the shift on the area results from the fact that particles occupy part of the interfacial area

available at the interface, which in turn become inaccessible for the surfactant molecules. Thus, calculating the area occupied for the particles, it is possible to obtain their contact angles [86, 87].

Another way for using the Π - A isotherms on the determination of the contact angle is through the evaluation of the area in which the collapse pressure appears for a particle-laden monolayer. This relies in the fact that at the collapse pressure it may be expected that particles at the fluid/fluid interface appear organized in a close-packed configuration. Thus, the use of geometric considerations allows one to estimate a value for the particle contact angle [88-90].

The use of methods based on the capillary rise has been also exploited for evaluating the contact angle of different types of particles [91-93]. These methods evaluate the contact angle from the analysis of the rate of capillary rising of a liquid column through a packed bed of particles. This allows determining the contact angle assuming that the packed bed is a bundle of capillary tubes with circular section and a radius, R_{eq} , and that the rising is only driven by the capillary pressure. Thus, it is possible to determine the contact angle from the following expression

$$h_L^2 = \frac{\gamma_{12} R_{eq} \cos \theta}{2\eta} t, \quad (11)$$

with h_L , t and η being the height of the penetrating liquid, the time and the viscosity of the rising liquid, respectively.

It is also possible to obtain an indirect evaluation of the wettability of powders by using a force tensiometer [94]. This requires loading the powder in a packed state into a spring-loaded which is hung onto the sample hook of the force tensiometer and then dipped into the liquid. Thus, it is possible to evaluate the changes of the mass over the time as the liquid penetrates into the powder bed, which allows determining the contact angle using the Washburn equation defined as follows

$$\cos \theta = \frac{m^2 \eta}{C \rho^2 \gamma_{12} t}, \quad (12)$$

where C and m represent a constant characteristic of the material and the mass change at a fixed value of the wetting time.

A last indirect approach is based on the determination of the contact angle by using the Atomic Force Microscope for evaluation the interaction of a colloidal probe and a liquid bubble by measuring the force-distance curve [95, 96].

2.3.2 Direct methods for multiple particles. The use of methodologies enabling the freezing [80] or gelling [97] of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces allows trapping the particles at the interface. Thus, it is possible to use Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) or AFM for evaluating the

particle heights from the interface, which by simple geometry considerations allows calculating the contact angle. The main advantage of this approach is the possibility to evaluate many particles from each individual measurement. However, it is necessary to apply a significant manipulation to the interface that may modify the locations of the particles, induce particle deformations or change the system composition.

The gel trapping technique (GTT) is probably the first introduced direct method, and it was initially proposed for evaluating the contact angle of microparticles at a fluid/fluid interface by their transference to a solid matrix which enables a direct visualization by using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) [97], and it was quickly extended to the study of nanoparticles by the use of Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) [74, 78]. In brief, the GTT relies on the replacement of the aqueous subphase by a solution including a non-surface active gelling agent, which after their gelation leads to the trapping of the particles on the gel surface, and enables the transference of the fluid/fluid interface to a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) replica which can be directly observe by using a suitable microscope. This allows one to obtain the contact angle from the analysis of the image. This approach has been exploited for evaluating the contact angle of particles at both liquid/vapor and liquid/liquid interface [44, 78, 97].

An alternative to the conventional GTT can be obtained using the approach introduced by Vogel et al. [98]. This relies on trapping the colloids in their positions at the water/vapour interface by adding butylcyanoacrylate to the interface *via* the vapour phase. Thus, the formation of poly(butylcyanoacrylate) starts upon contact with water, entrapping the colloids in their equilibrium positions. The obtained samples can be latter analysed using SEM or AFM as was above discussed for the PDMS replicas obtained during the GTT process.

An improvement on the determination of the contact angle in relation to the GTT may be obtained by the use of freeze fracture shadow-casting (FreSCa) coupled to cryo-SEM imaging. Thus, it is possible to determine the contact angle of particles with a minimal diameter of 10 nm. This approach relies on the determination of the contact angle by frozen the particle-laden interface to obtain a solid sample, which enables the immobilization of the particles. The fracture of the solid samples allows the exposure of the immobilized particles which later undergo an unidirectional metal-coating at a given angle, and then the contact angle is determined using geometrical assumptions from the height of the section of particles exposed using SEM imaging [60, 80, 99, 100]. The use of this approach for determining contact angles is very promising because it allows studying interfaces that are difficult assessed by other techniques. Furthermore, FreSCa enables the analysis of large regions of the particle-laden interface which provides an evaluation of the heterogeneity

of the contact angle distribution within the interface. However, a main limitation of this technique is the impossibility to evaluate the contact angle of extremely hydrophilic particles as result of the lower value of accesible casting angle.

Another indirect approach for evaluating the contact angle of multiple particles which differs significantly from the above described methods is the use of ellipsometry. This approach is a non-invasive method for determining the contact angle of sub-micrometer particles at fluid/fluid interfaces [79, 101]. This approach relies on the definition of the particle-laden interface as a bilayer, with the first layer corresponding to the fraction of the particles and subphase just below the interfacial plane, whereas the second layer is formed for the fraction of the particles and fluid remaining just above the interfacial plane. The analysis of the ellipsometry data makes necessary to consider the existence of two independent media with homogeneous reflectance, and hence the scattering phenomena are neglected. Thus, it is possible to establish a relationship between the contact angle of the particles and the thickness of the two layers using the Effective Medium Approach (EMA) for modelling the response of the interface [33, 58, 79, 101].

The use of interferometric techniques may also help of the determination of the contact angle of multiple particles as demonstrated Horozov et al. [102] with the film-calliper method. This method relies on the fabrication of particle bridges by the attachment of particles to both surfaces of a free-standing liquid film. Once, the formation of stable particle bridges is ensured, the analysis of the interference pattern obtained by optical microscopy allows calculating the contact angle.

2.3.3 Direct methods for single particle. The use of different microscopies allows determining the absolute position of particles, and the contact angle can be determined from the particle heights as in other methods. However, the advantage of this approach relies on the fact that the measurement is directly performed in the interface, and no manipulation are required, which ensures a clean measurement. On the other side, the methods based on a direct microscopy analysis are difficult to implement because they require very specific optics and illumination sources.

Snoeyink et al. [81] introduced the possibility to evaluate the contact angle by using Bessel beam microscopy (BBM), which allows observing the flotation height of the particles. From such height, it is possible to determine the contact angle of the particles at the fluid/fluid interface. The use of BBS allows studying particles with sizes between 10 nm and several micrometer, with no need of calibration.

Other approach for evaluating the contact angle of particles is exploiting a single-molecule localization microscopy, the so-called interface Point Accumulation for Imaging in Nanoscale Topography (iPAINT) [103, 104].

This methodology relies on a selective visualization of both the interface and the particles by labelling with suitable dyes. Thus, by switching the irradiation beam it is possible a selective excitation of the interface and the particles, enabling a direct visualization of the particle positions, lateral dimension and flotation heights, which makes it possible to calculate the contact angle. However, the labelling process may modify the force balance, altering the contact angles. It should be noted that this approach also allows evaluating lateral deformations on the interface.

A last technique used for a direct evaluation of the position of the particles at the interface is the use holographic imaging microscopy [37].

3. Interfacial tension minimization as driving force of the stabilization of particle-laden fluid/fluid interface

The particle trapping at fluid/fluid interfaces is guided by a decrease of the interfacial tension in relation to that corresponding to the clean fluid/fluid interface γ_{12} , which results in a decrease of the free energy associated with the formation of an interface, i.e. a decrease of the contact area between the two fluid phases [45, 49, 52, 105-107]. This may be understood in terms of the interfacial tension meaning: (i) force per unit of length acting tangentially at the interface along the contact line between the two phases, or (ii) energy cost, G_γ , resulting from the creation of one unit of contact area, A , between two immiscible fluid phases at given pressure (p) and temperature (T) values, i.e. $\gamma = \left(\partial G_\gamma / \partial A\right)_{T,p}$ [108].

It should be noted that the interfacial tension decrease associated with the assembly of particles at a fluid/fluid interface does not present a microscopic origin as occur for surfactant-laden interfaces because the trapping of the particles at the fluid/fluid interface, even for close-packed films, results in the of regions where the interfacial tension remains unchanged. Therefore, the interfacial tension for particle-laden interfaces may be only understood from a macroscopic perspective, and hence it should be considered as an effective magnitude, with its reduction being associated with the emergence of a 2D lateral pressure Π that counteracts the contraction of the interfacial area induced by the action of the interfacial tension. The origin of such interfacial pressure is the entropy and the inter-particle interactions, and allows defining the interfacial tension γ of the particle-laden interface as $\gamma = \gamma_{12} - \Pi$. Thus, the increase in the interfacial packing of the particle-laden interface results in a measurable decrease of the interfacial tension, which can be evaluated using the common methodologies used for interfacial tension determination [18, 32, 51, 109-114].

A closer look to the interfacial tension reduction of the fluid/fluid interface as result of the particle trapping evidences that the most important contribution appears from

the reduction of the area between the two fluids. In particular, when small particles with a free exchange between the bulk and the interface are considered, the interfacial excess concentration, Γ , is well defined and correlated to the total number of particles, N . This allows defining the effective interfacial tension of the particle-laden interface as

$$\gamma = \left(\frac{\partial G_\gamma}{\partial A}\right)_\Gamma = \left(\frac{\partial G_\gamma}{\partial A}\right)_{N,T,p} \quad (13)$$

It was above discussed that the adsorption of a particles to the fluid/fluid interface results in an energy change defined by ΔE_p , which results in a contribution to the reduction of the interfacial tension given by $\Delta E_p/A$. Thus, at low interfacial excess concentration, i.e. inter-particle interactions are neglected, it is possible to define the effective interfacial tension of the particle-laden fluid/fluid interface as [115]

$$\gamma = \gamma_{12} - \Pi(\Gamma), \quad (14)$$

with $\Pi(\Gamma) = \Gamma \Delta E_p$. This relationship provides a reasonable description of the experimental results as was demonstrated by Du et al. [115] for micro- and nano-particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces. Assuming that the change of the interfacial tension due to the incorporation of particles depends on both the interfacial particle density and the particle contact angle, it is possible by combining Equations (7) and (14) to define the interfacial tension of the particle-laden interface as follows [116]

$$\gamma = \gamma_{12} [1 + \eta(1 \pm \cos \theta)^2], \quad (15)$$

with $\eta = \pi \Gamma R^2$ being the area fraction occupied by the particles at the fluid/fluid interface [117, 118].

3.1 Thermodynamic description of particle-laden at fluid/fluid interfaces

The above discussion does not consider the role of the inter-particle interactions, which is critical for obtaining a physically insightful thermodynamic description. This is only possible by considering the effect of the wetting of the particles for the fluid/fluid interface and the inter-particle interactions on the interfacial pressure, and the chemical potentials of the particles at the fluid/fluid interface and in the bulk [114, 119, 120]. This appears more elusive for particle-laden interfaces than for typical amphiphilic molecules, mainly because the different sizes of colloidal particles and solvent molecules limits the application of conventional state equations in their canonical representation [121, 122]. Therefore, the thermodynamic description of colloidal particles trapped at fluid/fluid interfaces requires the development of a new thermodynamic framework.

The first attempt to provide a thermodynamic description of particle-laden interfaces was performed by Henderson [123] defining the particle-laden interface (2D colloidal suspension) as a hard disk fluid, where only excluded volume interactions are possible. This model is not realistic because it does not account for the surface pressure changes appearing at low coverage due to long-range electrostatic repulsion.

Binks [124] proposed a more refined model combining the Volmer and the van der Waals equations, with the former contribution accounting for the absence of lateral interactions between particles at low packing density, and the later describing the lateral interaction between the particles occurring at high packing density. Furthermore, two main assumptions were included in the model: (i) particles behave as surfactant molecules, and (ii) the area of each particle is defined by its geometrical area. However, this model also fails because it only consider the emergence of inter-particle interactions at the highest packing densities, even though experimental evidences have demonstrated their importance also for long separation distances. Therefore, the differences on the length scales involved in particle-laden and surfactant-laden interfaces results in an unrealistic description of the variation of the interfacial tension with the interfacial coverage. This is clear considering that for small particles (diameter < 1nm), the above model only predicts a significant change of the interfacial pressure at high interfacial coverages (50-70% of the total interfacial area). The group of Miller provided a more realistic interpretation of the thermodynamic behaviour of particle trapped at fluid/fluid interfaces, overcoming some of the limitations of the above commented models [125-127]. This model is an extension of their previous work on the description of the thermodynamic behaviour of protein-laden fluid/fluid interfaces [128], including some specific aspects describing the behaviour of particles trapped at the interface. This allows a definition of the interfacial pressure for a particle-laden fluid/fluid interface given by

$$\Pi = \frac{k_B T}{\omega_0} \left[\ln \left(1 - \frac{\omega}{A} \right) + \left(\frac{\omega}{A} \right) \right] - \Pi_{coh}, \quad (16)$$

with ω/A and ω_0 accounting for the interfacial coverage and the particle area, respectively and Π_{coh} being the so-called cohesion pressure, which is a parameter that accounts for the inter-particle interactions occurring within the interfacial film. This model provides a good description of the behavior of particles trapped at a fluid/fluid interface for coverages that are far from a close-packed state, with independence of the chemical nature or size of the studied particles.

Hua et al. [116, 129] proposed an alternative model based on experimental results. This model considers separately the effect on the surface tension of the reduction of the contact line between both fluid due to the particle attachment and the

inter-particle interactions. The former contribution, Π_p , associated with the wetting was obtained by measuring the particle density at the fluid/fluid interface, whereas the second one, Π_{p-p} , was obtained from measurements of the interfacial pressure of the 2D particle-laden interface by assuming a linear additivity $\Pi = \Pi_p + \Pi_{p-p}$. Upon the evaluation of the above mentioned contributions to the interfacial pressure and using the Frumkin model, which accounts for non-ideal interactions, under the assumption of thermodynamic equilibrium conditions (i.e. the Gibbs relationship is fulfilled), it was found that the interfacial pressure may be described through the following expression [130]

$$\Pi = -k_B T \Gamma_\infty \left[\ln(1 - \vartheta) - 0.5 K \vartheta^2 \right], \quad (17)$$

where Γ_∞ and K represent the interfacial excess concentration for a close-packed particle-laden interface and the inter-particle interaction constant, respectively, and $\vartheta = \Gamma/\Gamma_\infty$ accounts for the coverage fraction of the interface, i.e. the affinity of the particles for the fluid/fluid interface.

A last approach for accounting for the thermodynamic behavior of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces was proposed by Groot and Stoyanov [131]. This models introduces a dependence of the inter-particle interactions on the packing density through the following expression for the interfacial pressure

$$\Pi = \frac{4k_B T}{\pi d^2} \left[\frac{byZ}{\lambda} - b_2 \vartheta^2 \right], \quad (18)$$

where d provides an evaluation of the distance within the long-range interactions occurs, and Z accounts for the compressibility factor [132]. $(\lambda)^{1/2}$ represents the effective diameter of the particles, and b and b_2 are parameters accounting for the inter-particle interactions. This model showed a good potential for describing the behavior of soft gel particles trapped at fluid/fluid interfaces as was demonstrated by the studies by Deshmukh et al. [133].

The above discussion has pointed out that the thermodynamic description of particle-laden interfaces is far from clear, and showed that the description of the interfacial tension changes due to the attachment of particles to a fluid/fluid interface is challenging. Therefore, the development of more realistic models providing a thermodynamic framework for describing particle-laden interfaces requires a careful examination of two main contributions: (i) inter-particle interactions, and (ii) wettability of the particles. Furthermore, the inclusion of morphological and structural aspects of the particle-laden interface may be helpful for a more realistic description of the true thermodynamic behavior of particle-laden interfaces.

4. How particles interact within fluid/fluid interfaces?

The above discussion showed that both particle wetting and interfacial tension decrease present a central role for controlling the formation of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces. Nevertheless, a whole description of these type of systems is only possible by including the contribution of the inter-particle interactions [28, 42, 43, 119]. This is because a complex interplay between different type of interactions (electrostatic, van der Waals, hydrogen or covalent bonds) controls particle organization and dynamics within the fluid/fluid interface, and as matter of fact, affects to the physico-chemical properties of the assembled systems, and their potential applications [134, 135]. For particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces, the energetic landscape can be roughly defined by the difference between the chemical potentials of particles trapped at the fluid/fluid interface, μ_{int} , and dispersed in the bulk, μ_b , [136]

$$\Delta\mu = \mu_{int} - \mu_b, \quad (19)$$

which contains different contributions

$$\Delta\mu(\phi, \vartheta) = \Delta E_p + \mu_i(\phi, \vartheta) + \mu_e(\phi, \vartheta), \quad (20)$$

with ΔE_p , μ_i and μ_e defining the contributions of particle wettability, interactions and entropic contributions, respectively. ϕ and ϑ represent the volume fraction of particles in the bulk and the interfacial coverage, respectively. ΔE_p introduces the contribution of the contact angle to the energetic landscape defined according Equation (7) and μ_e represent the unfavorable entropic contribution associated with the reduction of the translational freedom degrees of the particles due to their attachment to the interface. μ_i includes all the interactions occurring between particles at fluid/fluid interfaces, e.g. van der Waals, electrostatic, capillary, fluctuations or hydrophobic. The origin of such interactions is the inter-particle coupling, that appears to be strongly dependent on the inter-particle distance, i.e. particle interfacial density. Figure 6 presents a sketch including different types of interactions which can appear within particle-laden interfaces.

It should be noted that the discussion of the interactions occurring in particle-laden interfaces must start from the consideration of their differences with the corresponding 3D counterpart systems, which arise from the existence of the interface acting as a confining environment. Therefore, particles trapped at a fluid/fluid interface must be considered as object attached to a fluctuating surface that separates to continuous phases with different physico-chemical properties. Furthermore, the behavior of such discontinuity is affected by the specific characteristics of the attached colloids, e.g. particle size and shape; charge density and wettability, or surface chemistry [28, 29, 42, 43, 51, 137, 138]. The combination of the above-mentioned aspects makes it difficult to provide a quantitative description of the

interactions operating in particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces. This section will briefly summarized the main interactions affecting to the assembly of particles at fluid/fluid interfaces, i.e. the term μ_i . Thus in a broad perspective, such interactions may be divided in three main categories [29]. The first one includes the direct interactions, that are related to the characteristics of the assembled particles, e.g. size, shape, surface chemistry, charge and roughness. This type of interactions also appears in bulk dispersions, and are modified as result of the presence of the interface, e.g. electrostatic, hydrophobic and van der Waals interactions. The second type of interactions includes those emerging as result of the confinement within the interface, e.g. capillary ones. The last type of interactions are associated with the presence of external fields acting on individual objects or ensembles of them.

Figure 6. Idealized picture of different types of interactions appearing in particle-laden fluid interfaces. (a) Repulsive dipolar and Coulomb interactions, and van der Waals and capillary attractive forces. (b) Attractive hydrophobic forces and steric repulsions. (c) Solvation-mediated interactions. Adapted from Maestro et al. [42], Copyright (2019), with permission from Elsevier.

4.1 Direct interactions

The direct interactions in colloid trapped at fluid/fluid interfaces emerge mainly from the specific nature of the concerned particles. The description of these interactions appears as paramount for understanding the assembly of particle layers at the interface. However, the current knowledge of these interactions is very limited due to the complexity associated with the analysis of the different repulsive and attractive contributions, which in many cases involve many body interactions [29].

4.1.1 Van der Waals interactions. The van der Waals, London-van der Waals or dispersion forces are ubiquitous in chemical systems, emerging from the interaction between the individual components of the particles [76, 139, 140]. The introduction of the van der Waals contribution to the balance of interactions of a particle-laden interface appears less straightforward than for particle dispersions, and requires to consider an effective Hamaker constant, which depends on the volume fraction of particle immersed in the fluid 2 ($f=(1-\cos\theta)/2$) [28, 43, 141]. Thus, it is possible to consider, in the energetic balance, the differences on the inter-particle interactions for particles in a bulk media and trapped at the fluid/fluid, by using an effective Hamaker constant H for the inter-particle interaction within an arbitrary interface defined as

$$H = H_{P1} + f^2(3 - 2f)(H_{P2} - H_{P1}), \quad (21)$$

with H_{P1} and H_{P2} being the Hamaker constants across fluid 1 and fluid 2, respectively. Thus, it is possible to assume that the strength of the van der Waals interactions will depend on f , i.e. the particle wettability and the relative values of H_{P1} and H_{P2} . This can result in van der Waals interactions stronger or weaker than those emerging for particles totally immersed in one of the fluids. The average van der Waals interaction between a pair of particles at a fluid/fluid interface can be defined as

$$E_{vdW} = -\frac{A}{12} \left(\frac{2R}{r - 2R} \right), \quad (22)$$

with r being the distance between particle centers. It should be mentioned that a similar interaction potential provides a quantitative description of the growth of anisotropic particle domains controlled by an asymmetrical distribution of the interactions within the interface [142-144]. Van der Waals force between two identical bodies are always attractive, whereas those occurring between bodies with different nature can be either attractive or repulsive [145]. However, in most particle-laden interfaces, van der Waals interactions present a very limited influence ($0.1-1k_B T$) [28], and only start to play an important role when particles are placed very close to each other, which is not common due to strong repulsive contributions. Nevertheless, the van der Waals contribution always appears stronger for particle-laden interfaces than for particle dispersions [28, 140, 146].

4.1.2 Electrostatic interactions. The electrostatic interactions play a very important role when charged particles are considered, emerging from the combination of the repulsive screened coulombic repulsion which operates at short distances (also found in bulk suspensions), and a long-range attractive dipole-dipole interaction as result of the particle trapping at the fluid/fluid interface. Thus, the overall

electrostatic interaction potential for particles attached to fluid/fluid interfaces can be written as [147]

$$E_{electrostatic} = \frac{a_1 k_B T}{3r} e^{-\kappa r} + \frac{a_2 k_B T}{r^3}, \quad (23)$$

with a_1 and a_2 being pre-factors which weight the importance of the screened Coulomb potential and the dipolar interaction, respectively. For inter-particle distances long enough ($\kappa r \gg 10$, where κ is the inverse Debye screening length), the dipolar interaction is the main component of the electrostatic contribution [148, 149].

The dipolar contribution occurs across the fluid phases, and consequently is expected to be strongly dependent on the chemical nature of such phases, in particular on their dipolar constant. Furthermore, the interfacial plane induces a clear asymmetry on this interaction [3]. Thus, for an interface between water and a non-polar phase, the dipole is defined between the charges on the particle surface and the counterions dissociated in the bulk for the part of the particle immersed in water, and between the surface charges on the particle surface and the image charges appearing in the water for the part of the particles immersed in the oil phase [28]. The asymmetry on the distribution of the dipolar contribution results in a critical impact of the wetting properties on the interactions. Thus, considering that a particle is transported from an aqueous continuous phase to the water/non-polar phase interface, it is not expected any variation on the interaction across the aqueous part, whereas in the non-polar phase it will be energetically favorable the neutralization of the surface groups, which will lead to an asymmetry in the double layer. This is important considering that the interactions between planes with the same charge is always repulsive, whereas those interactions involving planes of different charge can appear as attractive or repulsive depending on their relative separations [76]. Therefore, the overall interaction between particles at fluid/fluid interfaces may be dependent on different parameters, e.g. the volume fraction of particle immersed in each fluid, the dielectric constants, and degree of screening in the aqueous phase [150, 151].

4.1.3 Hydrophobic interactions. These interactions appear from the important attraction that undergoes hydrophobic surfaces in water. However, there is no any systematic discussion about this type of interactions in the literature yet, and hence their theoretical description remains a challenge.

The hydrophobic interactions increase their role as the particle size is decreased, which is explained considering that as the length scale of the particles is reduced, the molecular details of the solvent and the interface start to play a non-negligible role in the interaction balance. Therefore, the emergence of hydrophobic interactions appears mandatory to minimize the unfavorable particle-solvent contacts [92, 152, 153].

4.1.4 Steric interactions. The stabilization of colloidal dispersions by adding polymer additives is very frequent because it can exert an osmotic pressure upon their confinement between two particles [145]. This polymer can be either adsorbed by physical interactions within the particle surface or grafted through covalent bonds, with their configuration being limited for the coverage and the quality of the solvent, which results in different interaction potentials [43]. In all the case, the steric force presents a repulsive character, with the osmotic pressure emerging in the region of the overlapping polymer chains preventing the aggregation of the particles as result of the unfavourable entropy decrease associated with the compression of the solvated chains [145].

The steric contribution can be defined by the Derjaguin approximation as follows

$$E_{steric} = RL^2\sigma^{3/2} \left(\frac{2L}{r-2R} \right)^{1/4}, \quad (24)$$

with L and σ being the effective length of steric repulsions and the maximum brush length, respectively. It should be noted that the brush in particle-laden interface becomes asymmetric, which makes very difficult to determine L . The introduction of steric repulsion mechanisms is a very useful tool for obtain monolayers of particles with tunable interactions [43].

4.2 Interactions mediated for the presence of an interface

Among the interactions appearing as result of the confinement of particles at a fluid/fluid interface, capillary ones are probably those having a stronger impact on the energetic landscape of the interfaces [154]. These interactions emerge from the deformation of the fluid/fluid interface appearing as result of the particle adsorption. This increases the lateral interaction between colloidal particles at the interface. Figure 7 shows a sketch of the different types of capillary forces that can appears in particle-laden interfaces.

Capillary interactions are strongly dependent on the particle size. Thus, the interface may be significantly deformed as result of the gravity and buoyancy forces in combination with the wetting properties of the particles for big particles. This results in the so-called flotation forces, which present less importance as the particle size is reduced. These flotation forces may be considered negligible for particles with sizes smaller than the capillary length of the fluid/fluid interface ($l_c = \Delta\rho g / \gamma_{12}$, with $\Delta\rho$ being the density difference between the two fluid phases), and in practice their role is negligible for particles with size below 5-10 μm . This is explained considering that the weight of small particles is not high enough to induce a significant

deformation of the fluid/fluid interface. However, this does not mean that capillary interaction does not play any role on the energetic landscape of small particles, emerging the so-called immersion forces, which depends mostly on the wetting properties of the particles. The origin of these forces is the existence of a non-smooth contact line, i.e. particle adsorption originates undulation or other irregular shapes along the contact line.

Figure 7. Sketch of the different types of capillary forces appearing in particle-laden interfaces. Reprinted from Kralchevsky et al. [154], Copyright (2001), with permission from the American Chemical Society.

Neighboring particles are attracted or repelled, depending on the local curvature of the interface, by the overlapping of their respective interface deformations to ensure a minimization of the interfacial free energy of the system. This capillary interactions can be written as follows [155]

$$E_{capillary}(R) = -12\pi\gamma_{12}K^2\zeta \frac{r^4}{R^4}, \quad (25)$$

where ζ is a factor depending on the particle orientation and K a function of the deformation amplitude of the interface. The presence of charged colloids at the fluid/fluid interface leads to a direct electric repulsion, and/or electrocapillary and electro-dipping forces (electro-dipping forces consider single particles, and direct electric repulsion and electrocapillary forces involving multiple particles) [76], which are the result of dielectric constant differences between the two fluid phases. These interactions may induce a deformation of the interface which is comparable to that resulting from the action of the gravity in bigger particles [29, 156].

4.3 Externally-driven interactions

The use of external fields have been demonstrated as a very powerful tool for a tunable assembly of colloidal particles at fluid/fluid interfaces. Thus, it is possible to control, almost at will, the mechanical, optical and electronic properties of the assembled systems [11, 157].

The trapping of particles at fluid/fluid interfaces results in a restriction of the particle mobility in relation to the interfacial plane, with this being mainly controlled by the particle wettability. Therefore, it should be expected only small fluctuations of the particles around their equilibrium positions in relation to the interfacial after being placed in their equilibrium positions. However, the mobility within the interfacial plane does not present any constrain, and the particles are free of diffusing within such plane [158]. This motion within the interface plane may be manipulated by the mechanical deformation of the interface, e.g. changes of the area (dilatational deformations) or shape (shear deformations). Thus, it is possible to tune the characteristic of the interfacial assembly and induce 2D phase transitions [46, 159, 160]. The application of magnetic or electric fields can lead to similar effects when responsive particles are used [161, 162].

Moreover, the change of the environmental conditions (pH, temperature or ionic strength) may be also used for modifying the interactions and the organization of particles at the fluid/fluid interface (see Figure 6c). This can be also used to tune the assembly of the particles at the interface as has been explored for the assembly of microgel particles [133, 140, 163].

5. Adsorption dynamics

The adsorption kinetics of colloidal particles from a fluid bulk phase to a fluid/fluid interface appears as a very complex process, and the current understanding about this problem is scarce [47, 117, 122, 140, 162, 164-168].

Assuming the adsorption of charged colloidal particles to a fluid/fluid interface, it may be assumed that the electrostatic interactions between the interface and the particles should influence the adsorption process (*Note that it is commonly assumed that both water/vapor and water/non-polar fluid interfaces present a negative effective charge* [169, 170]). This leads to a situation in which negative particles adsorb very slowly or not at all, whereas positive one always adsorb to the fluid/fluid interface, with the adsorption behavior being modulated by the ionic strength [171]. Furthermore, the role of the particles wettability cannot be neglected in this process [37, 45, 47, 172].

Assuming that there are no neither adsorption barrier nor external flow fields, it is possible to assume that the transport of the particles can be governed by a Fickian diffusion analogous to the one defined by Ward and Tordai for molecular surfactants [173], where the mass transport rate is given as

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial x^2}, \quad (26)$$

with c being the bulk concentration, D the diffusion coefficient of the particles and x and t the distance from the interface and the diffusion time, respectively. Assuming for the time dependent surface concentration $\Gamma(t)$ that at $t=0$, the adsorption at the interface is negligible, i.e. $\Gamma(t=0) = 0$, and considering a homogenous bulk distribution of the particles, i.e. $c(x, 0) = c_\infty$, it is possible to write a boundary condition for the adsorption process as follows

$$\frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial t} = D \left[\frac{\partial c(x, t)}{\partial x} \right]_{z=0}, \quad (27)$$

and hence assuming that the adsorption occurs in absence of barriers, and that the interfacial density is small enough to ensure that the concentration of the bulk is not significantly reduced by the adsorption, i.e. $c(\infty, t) \rightarrow c_\infty$, the combination of Equations (26) and (27) results in the Ward-Tordai approach [173]. If the adsorption is considered irreversible and there is a complete depletion of the sublayer, the time dependence of Γ can be expressed as follows

$$\Gamma(t) = 2c_\infty \sqrt{\frac{Dt}{\pi}}. \quad (28)$$

The above definition of the adsorption process does not account for the presence of any adsorption barrier. The presence of an adsorption barrier requires an extended framework, which includes additional terms to the adsorption model. Figure 8 displays a sketch of the energetic landscape emerging from the adsorption process.

Figure 8. Energetic landscape emerging for the adsorption of a particle to a fluid/fluid interface. Note that the energetic barrier $\Delta E_{\text{barrier}}$ increases as the coverage increases. Reprinted from Deshmukh et al. [140], Copyright (2015), with permission from Elsevier.

The additional terms associated with the adsorption barriers are described using different functional forms. Thus, electrostatic interactions are generally accounted by the incorporation of an exponential term [174], whereas the

effect of steric factors, i.e. the coverage, is commonly accounted introducing a linear term [140].

The impact of the adsorption barriers for the incorporation of nanoparticles at a fluid/fluid interface was evidenced on the study by Schwenke et al. [117]. They found that the adsorption of particles was dominated by a slow dynamical process as the coverage was increased, with the emergence of local ordering processes at the interface that were directly related to adsorption events driving the process at high interface coverage. This was in agreement with the results by Deshmukh et al. [140]. They found that the adsorption of microgel particles at water/vapor interfaces can be defined in terms of two regimes: (i) at short times, diffusion-controlled adsorption, and (ii) at long times, the coverage increases, and steric barrier appears and hinders the adsorption of additional particles.

Dugyala et al. [175] explored the adsorption of negatively charged silica nanoparticles to the water/decane interface, and found important results in relation to the impact of the barriers on the adsorption kinetics. Highly charged particles showed a negligible adsorption at the fluid/fluid interface. This may be explained considering that they experience an energy barrier as they are close to the interface, whereas this barrier is overcome when salt is added for screening the particle surface charges. This latter favors the migration and adsorption of the particles to the interface. The origin of the energy barrier, obtained from the dynamic surface tension data in terms of the Ward-Tordai approach in the short time limit [173], was found in good agreement with the idea of an inhibited adsorption of highly charged particles as result of the image charge repulsion. This leads to a modified adsorption model including an effective diffusivity which accounts for the adsorption barrier [176, 177]

$$\Gamma(t) = -2c_0\Delta E_p \sqrt{\frac{D_{eff}t}{\pi}}, \quad (29)$$

with c_0 representing the solution concentration for $t \rightarrow 0$, and D_{eff} the effective diffusivity defined as

$$D_{eff} = D \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta E_{barrier}}{k_B T}\right), \quad (30)$$

where $\Delta E_{barrier}$ defines the energy of the barrier.

5.1 Particles desorption from the fluid/fluid interface

The above discussion has underlined that desorption of particles trapped at fluid/fluid interfaces is not, in most of the cases, a spontaneous process. This is the result of the high energy associated with the trapping process (several times the thermal energy $k_B T$). However, desorption can emerge as a very important phenomenon under very specific conditions [178, 179]. In the following, a brief discussion on the

desorption process involving particles trapped at fluid/fluid interfaces is presented.

The removal of particles from fluid/fluid interfaces is a very important challenge for developing application in which the recovery and regeneration of the particles at the end of the process is mandatory, e.g. biocatalysis, gas storage or biomass conversion [180-182].

The desorption of nanoparticles can be achieved by modifying the fluid phases or the interface, e.g. addition of surface active molecules, modification of the interaction balance within the interface (ionic strength or pH changes) [183-186].

Garbin et al. [168] demonstrated that the desorption of nanoparticles can be forced upon application of a compressional stress to the particle-laden interface. This compressional stress was demonstrated to be about $10^2 k_B T$. The importance of the strength of the mechanical perturbation for forcing the expulsion of nanoparticles from the fluid/fluid interface was explored by Poulichet and Garbin [178]. They apply ultrafast compressional deformations to the interface by the use of ultrasound, and found that particles can be expelled from the interface only in those particle-laden interfaces in which the trapping energy of the particles is not high enough to consider an irreversible desorption or there are no strong inter-particle interactions within the interface. Otherwise, the ejection of particles from the interface makes necessary to deform the interface in such a way that can be induced a tangential viscous drag force exceeding the inter-particle interactions.

6. Ordering particles at fluid/fluid interfaces: a brief approach to morphological and structural issues

The description of the assembly of particles at fluid/fluid interfaces requires paying some attention to some relevant morphological and structural aspects of particle-laden systems. The understanding of the ordering of particles at fluid/fluid interfaces makes necessary to face two main problems: (i) distribution of the particles within the quasi-2D fluid/fluid interface, and (ii) position of the particles in relation to the interfacial plane, i.e. particle contact angles.

Santini et al. [32] demonstrated that the interfacial organization of hydrophilic silica with negative charge at the water/vapor interface may be modulated by the addition of the cationic surfactant CTAB (hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide). This can be understood considering that the surfactant can modify the wettability of the particles, and as matter of fact, the position of the particles in relation to the interfacial plane [33]. Thus, the different wettability of the particles can induce a different packing on the particle-laden fluid/fluid interface, and consequently different interfacial morphology in agreement with the findings by Zang et al. [187] for silica particles hydrophobized by chemical silanization adsorbed at water/vapor interfaces. Therefore,

there is a close correlation between the particle wettability and their packing at fluid/fluid interfaces.

Santini et al. [51] deepened on the effect of the particles hydrophobicity on the interfacial morphology, and found that for particles with the lowest hydrophobicity, the adsorption proceeds with the formation of isolated particles rafts which grow until the formation of a close-packed particle laden interface as the hydrophobicity of the particles is increased. This increase of the interfacial coverage is also reflected by a strong decrease of the surface tension and a sharp increase of the interfacial excess concentration determined by ellipsometry. Similar densification was found by Bykov et al. [109, 188, 189] and Yazhgur et al. [110, 188] for polystyrene sulfate latex micro- and nanoparticles and silica nanoparticles decorated with CTAB at both water/vapor and water/alkane interfaces. Therefore, the above results indicate that the increase of the particle hydrophobicity allows tuning the packing at the interfacial layer, leading to a transition from lost-packed particle-laden interfaces layer to close packed one.

The densification of the particle-laden interface depends on a complex balance of interactions as was evidenced for silica nanoparticles-decorated with CTAB by Li-Destri et al. [190] using Grazing incidence small angle X-ray scattering (GISAXS). They found that independently of the surfactant concentration, the long range interactions were electrostatic in origin, whereas the origin of the short range interactions may be different depending on the CTAB concentration, and its reorganization around the particles. Thus, at low surfactant concentrations, it was found steric repulsions associated with the CTAB molecules on the particle surface, whereas this interaction becomes of electrostatic origin with the increase of the CTAB concentration as result of the formation of bilayers on the water side. This results in an increase of the inter-particle repulsion, and consequently of the inter-particle distance.

Bonales et al. [191] explored the assembly of polystyrene sulfate latex with diameters ranging from 1.0 to 5.7 μm at the water/octane interface, and found qualitatively similar results to the above discussed for the densification of nanoparticle layers, with a transition between different phases emerging as the interfacial coverage increases. Furthermore, the transition between the different phases was shifted to lower interfacial density as the particle size decreases. This finding were in agreement with the studies performed independently by Parolini et al. [192]. Figure 9 displays optical microscopy images for microparticles at the water/octane interface together with their corresponding Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) and structure factors $S(q)$ obtained from the analysis of the organization of the particles at the fluid/fluid interface (representation of $S(q)$ vs. q , with q evaluating the inter-particle distances.

A detailed analysis of the optical microscopy images evidences clearly that the increase of the interfacial coverage results in an ordering of the particles at the fluid/fluid interface, with the order being reminiscent to that what happen for 3D systems. This is confirmed by the FFT images (see inserted panel in the optical microscope images of Figure 9). Thus, the fluid phases (gas and liquid) present a random set of points in their FFT images, whereas for the hexatic phase, and in particular for the solid one, the FFT images evidence the presence of a well-defined hexagonal pattern. On the other side, fluid-like (gas-like and liquid-like) does not show neither orientational nor positional order. Further details on the organization of the particle within the fluid/fluid interface are obtained from the analysis of the structure factor. At low interfacial coverage (see Figure 9a), $S(q)$ evidences the typical functional dependence expected for a gas, i.e. an initial increase from 0 to 1 and then remains constant. The increase of the interfacial coverage to enter on the liquid-phase (see Figure 9b) is evidenced from the structure factor by the appearance of few oscillations, which are almost exponentially damped with the increase of the inter-particle distance. This must be considered a reminiscence of the disappearance of the positional order on the liquid as the inter-particle distance increases. For the hexagonal 2D solid (see Figure 9d), the structure factor shows the typical narrow and intense peaks expected for an ordered phase, with the position of the maximum being placed at the characteristic distances expected for a hexagonal array and their multiples. This phase was found to have both positional and orientational order. On the contrary, the hexatic phase (see Figure 9c) presents orientational order but does not have positional one, and was found, independently of the particle size, as an intermediate state between liquid-like and solid-like monolayers in agreement with the predictions of the KTHNY theory [193, 194].

Bonales et al. [195] also studied monolayers formed for mixtures of particles with different sizes, and found that independently of the size ratio, the monolayers behavior appears intermediate between those corresponding to the individual systems, with the compositional ratio defining the true phase diagram. Following with the studies of microparticles at fluid/fluid interfaces, Martínez-Pedrero et al. [162] showed that the use of magnetic fields allows tuning the phase behavior of superparamagnetic microparticles at the fluid/fluid interface.

Kim et al. [196] showed that the organization of particles at fluid/fluid interfaces can be modulated by modifying the length of capping ligands adsorbed on the particle surface. In particular, they found that the increase of the length of the ligands can drive a transition from an ordered liquid phase to a disordered solid one. This was ascribed to an entropy-driven effect based on the emergence of steric constraints associated

with the restriction of the particle motion due to the presence of the ligand shell. It should be noted that the transition between solid-like and liquid-like phases occurs also with the formation of a hexatic phase, and hence the ligand-induced melting process may be considered analogous to a temperature-induced melting. However, the critical parameter, in this case, should be considered the ligand length.

Figure 9. Examples of images, FFT images and structure factors $S(q)$ for charged polystyrene microparticles trapped at the water/octane interface. The first set of images correspond to microparticles with diameter of 2.9 μm ; the second set correspond to microparticles with diameter of 5.7 μm ; the third set show microparticles with diameter of 1.6 μm , and the last one correspond to microparticles with diameter of 1.0 μm . Adapted from Bonales et al. [191], Copyright (2011), with permission from American Chemical Society.

Isa et al. [197] also explored the effect of the length of the capping ligand on the organization of colloidal particles at a fluid/fluid interface (water/decane interface) by using Fe_3O_4 particles capped with poly(ethyleneglycol) chains of different molecular weight. They found that the in-plane separation between the particles at full interfacial coverage depends strongly on the molecular weight of the tethered chains, which agrees with the differences on the organization reported by Kim et al. [196].

Very recently Rahman et al. [198] correlated the different phases appearing within particle-laden interfaces as the coverage was increased with the inter-particle interactions, and found that the degree of order appearing at the interface may be correlated to the strength of such interactions. Thus, disordered phases were found for systems in which the interactions were weakly repulsive or strongly attractive, whereas strong inter-particle repulsions lead to the formation of highly ordered hexagonal phase, with the hexatic phase appearing when the repulsive and attractive forces are equilibrated.

7. Dynamics of particles confined at a quasi-2D particle-laden interface

The interest for the dynamics and transport properties of particles trapped at fluid/fluid interface has undergone a noticeable growth in last years. This can be understood mainly as result of two different aspects: (i) fluid/fluid interfaces are good models for describing the behaviour of different chemical and biological systems, and (ii) the possibility to use the motion of colloidal particles at fluid/fluid interfaces as tracer for evaluating the mechanical response of the interfaces (i.e. their use in microrheology experiments) [34-36, 199-202].

In general, particle trapped at fluid/fluid interface can define a random motion parallel to the fluid/fluid interface, which presents many similarities with the motion of particles in a bulk liquid [203, 204]. The high energy associated with the trapping of particles at fluid/fluid interfaces makes negligible the motion perpendicular to the interface, and hence in the following only the translational diffusion parallel to the interfacial plane will be considered [205].

The study of the dynamics of particle at fluid/fluid interfaces is not straightforward and makes necessary to consider both inter-particle and particle-solvent interactions. Therefore, the motion of particles within the fluid/fluid interface is strongly limited for the hydrodynamics constrains imposed by the presence of two fluids surrounding the particles, which influence in the time-scales in which the dynamic processes of particles trapped at fluid/fluid interfaces occurs [35, 163, 206-210]. This is very different to that what happens for particles in bulk dispersions and leads, in most of the cases, to an increase of the diffusion

coefficient upon particle confinement within a 2D fluid/fluid interface [205]. However, this is strongly dependent on the difference between the viscosities of the two fluid phases; with the diffusion of particles embedded within fluid/fluid interface being enhanced as the viscosity difference between the fluid phases is reduced [211-213]. This suggests that the parallel viscous drag parallel to the interface for a trapped particle can be defined by an average of the drags corresponding to the two fluid weighted by the immersion depth in each of the fluids, i.e. the contact angle [36, 213]. However, the drag associated with fluid 2 can be neglected from the theoretical description of the dynamics of particles at fluid/fluid interfaces when its viscosity is much smaller than that of fluid 1 (see Figure 1) [214].

Recently, Villa et al. [36] reviewed the different hydrodynamic models accounting for the translational viscous drag of a particle at a fluid interface. They found that these models are based in different assumptions and cannot describe completely the experimental results for particles with sizes below few micrometers.

A detailed analysis of the dynamics of particle at fluid/fluid interfaces evidences that in the short time limit, the fluids behave in compressible-like way, and hence the colloidal motion may be assimilated to a sound wave defined by a characteristic time $t_s=R/c_s$, with R and c_s being the particle radius and the velocity of sound, respectively. This motion occur within time-scales around 10^{-1} ns, which makes difficult its measurement using conventional techniques. At longer times, the hydrodynamics interactions induce a second dynamics process, with a characteristic time, t_h . This motion results in a transverse momentum diffusing away from the particles, with the velocity field leading to a drag force between the particles. The time-scale involved in this type of motion arrives up to 10 ns, which is similar to the time required for diffusion of the transverse momentum along a distance comparable to the inter-particle distance. Furthermore, a motion associated with the decay of the initial velocity of a colloid appears commonly coupled to the motion resulting from the hydrodynamic interactions, which is a consequence of the impact of the time-dependent velocity field associated with the particle motion, and depends on the diffusion coefficient of the transverse momentum of the fluid.

The description of the particle dynamics can be performed in terms of a diffusion-controlled motion defined by a characteristic constant

$$D_0 = \frac{k_B T}{g}, \quad (31)$$

with g being the drag coefficient. In bulk systems, and for non-deformable particles $g=6\pi\eta R$, with η being the viscosity of the fluid, which gives the well-known Stokes-Einstein law. However, as was discussed above the definition of the

drag coefficient is more complex when particles embedded in a fluid/fluid interface are concerned, with the definition of the drag coefficient depending on both the viscosities of the fluid phases, and the relative immersion of the particle on each fluid layer [215].

The time-scale of the motion of particles at a fluid/fluid interface along a distance equivalent to their radius ranges between 1 ms and 1 s, which makes possible the separation of the colloidal diffusion and other motions. Therefore, the motion of particles at the fluid/fluid interface may be defined as an uncorrelated Brownian motion in the long time limit. However, this does not consider that several neighbours can surround each single particle, and this may modify the interactions due to the interactions [36, 162].

The use of videomicroscopy techniques allows a direct evaluation of the trajectories of particles at fluid/fluid interfaces, which offers a valuable information for the analysis of the dynamics of particle-laden interfaces. This information is generally obtained by calculating the mean square displacement, MSD ($\langle \Delta r^2(t) \rangle$), which can be defined in terms of the diffusion coefficient, D , and the characteristic length of the translational motion, d , as follows

$$\langle \Delta r^2(t) \rangle = 2dDt^\alpha, \quad (32)$$

with α being a scale exponent. At low interfacial coverage, the dependence of the MSD on t can be expected linear [162, 214]. However, as the interfacial coverage is increased, the interfacial dynamics becomes more complex, appearing a clear differentiation between the motion at short and long times. This is evidenced by the change on the slope of the dependence on the MSD on t . At short time, it can be expected that the particle motion appears limited to the region defined by their closer neighbours [216]. This leads to a self-diffusion coefficient for the short-time limit defined as

$$D_s = \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{\langle \Delta r^2 \rangle}{4t}. \quad (33)$$

The increase of the surface coverage, ϑ , results in a decrease of the diffusion coefficient in the short-time limit due to the impact of the interactions

$$D_s = \alpha D_0 (1 - \mu \vartheta), \quad (34)$$

with μ being a parameter accounting for the interactions [217]. At the longest times, the role of the collective motion of particles starts to be non-negligible, leading to a diffusion coefficient for the long time limit defined as

$$D_m = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle \Delta r^2 \rangle}{4t}, \quad (35)$$

with the dynamics response in the long-time limits being understood considering the escaping dynamics of a particle from the cage formed by their nearest neighbors, i.e. the α -relaxation [218-220]. At high interfacial coverage, the repulsions between the particles leads to the emergence of an arrested dynamics within the experimental accessible time scale [221]. This does not allow an analytical solution for the diffusion coefficient, which makes necessary to use independent Brownian Harmonic oscillator (BHO) as model. This approach results in particles following an extended Langevin equation where an elastic force has been included [222, 223]

$$m \frac{dv}{dx} = -gv + F(t) - kx, \quad (36)$$

where m and v indicate the mass of a particle and its velocity, respectively, and k represents the characteristic force constant of the elastic force acting on the particle, with $F(t)$ accounting for the random force. On the overdamped limit, and without considering the inertia, the following solution is obtained [218, 219]

$$\langle \Delta r^2(t) \rangle = 2d\delta^2 \left[1 - e^{-D_0 t / \delta^2} \right], \quad (37)$$

with $\delta^2 = k_B T / k$, and the characteristic time defined as

$$t_{BHO} = \frac{\delta^2}{D_0} = \frac{g}{k}. \quad (38)$$

It is common the introduction of *ad hoc* corrections for accounting for the dynamics of interacting Brownian particles. The introduction of a term that considers the non-exponential character of the decay provides a more complete description [224, 225]

$$\langle \Delta r^2(t) \rangle = 2d\delta^2 \left[1 - e^{-(D_0 t / \delta^2)^c} \right] \left(1 + \frac{D_0 t}{\delta^2} \right), \quad (39)$$

with the introduction of the stretching exponent c , and a term describing the long-term dynamics associated with the escaping of a single particle from particle ensembles returning again to the linear dependence of the MSD on time. It should be noted that the stretching exponent is a fitting parameter, which commonly assumes values below 1 and provides information about the width of the relaxation spectrum.

The above discussed model cannot describe the dynamics of solid-like monolayers, which can be solved partially by introducing the Overdamped Bead-Spring model (OBS) [226, 227]

$$m \frac{dv_i}{dt} = -gv_i(t) + F_i(t) - k \sum_j^m [u_j(t) - u_i(t)], \quad (40)$$

where $u_i(t)$ informs about the displacement of the particle i at time t , and mn provides the number of the nearest neighbours to i . For solid-like particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces, the escaping dynamics of individual particles from particle ensembles is hindered due to the high coverage, and it cannot be expected any linear increase of the MSD at long times. This leads to a solution for the OBS model, which reads as follows

$$\langle \Delta r^2(t) \rangle = \frac{2dk_B T}{kN} \sum_b \frac{1}{L(q_b)} \left[1 - e^{-kL(q_b)t/b} \right]. \quad (41)$$

Equation (40) only includes the interactions between closer neighbors, with the lattice factor being defined as

$$L(q_b) = \sum_j^m \left[1 - \cos(q_x n_j) \right]. \quad (42)$$

where q_b is the b^{th} wave vector of the relaxation mode q , and n_j takes into account a vector pointing from the point i of the lattice to its closer neighbour j . In the short time limit, the OBS model leads to a similar slope in the MSD than the BHO one in the initial stages, whereas in the long time the OBS mode tends to a limit value defined as

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \langle \Delta r^2(t) \rangle (t \rightarrow \infty) = \frac{2dk_B T}{kN} \sum_b \frac{1}{L(q_b)}, \quad (43)$$

with this long time limit depending on both the strength of the harmonic force and the lattice factor.

It should be noted that the quantitative analysis of the experimental MSD at fluid/fluid interfaces appears many times obscured due to different aspects: (i) the mechanical contributions of the bulk fluid phases; (ii) the mechanical coupling between the probe and the environment, and (iii) the distribution of the probe within the interface [228, 229].

8. Understanding the response of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces upon mechanical stresses

Particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces are characterized by a surface pressure, which acts in the opposite direction of the surface tension. This leads to the emergence of in-plane deformations (shear and dilation) of the interfaces due to the coupling between interfacial and bulk flows. Furthermore, in such complex fluid/fluid interfaces it also appears, under very specific stress conditions, several types of out-of-plane deformations, e.g. buckling, expulsion of material into the bulk or multilayer formation. Figure 10 shows an idealized picture of the different deformation modes that may appear

in particle-laden interfaces upon the application of mechanical stresses.

This can be studied by interfacial rheology, which is focused on the analysis of the flow and deformation of interface subjected to stress [35, 42, 119, 230]. The rheological response of particle-laden interfaces reflects the role of the thermodynamic and hydrodynamic interactions between particles and with the surrounding fluids. This complex can be only solved when the mechanical response of the layer is dominant in relation to that of the bulk fluids [231, 232]. The deformation of a particle-laden fluid/fluid interface is associated with two concurrent processes: (i) the amount or shape of the fluid/fluid interfaces is modified, and (ii) the particle layer at the interface is deformed. These processes require an energy input, and govern the mechanical properties of the interface, which can be described by the following expression [233, 234]

$$\sigma_{ij} = \gamma\delta_{ij} + T_{ij}, \quad (44)$$

with δ_{ij} and σ_{ij} being the Kronecker delta and the interfacial stress tensor. The expression of the surface stress tensor contains two terms associated with the different contributions to the interfacial stress. The first term is associated with the surface energy which accounts for the energetic cost associated with the fluid/fluid interface itself, and for any adsorption/desorption processes, which may change the interfacial tension. Furthermore, this term also accounts for Marangoni stresses associated with spatial surface tension gradients. The second term is the anisotropic tensor (T_{ij}), and account for the cost of deforming the particle layer [114, 235-237].

Figure 10. Different phenomena occurring in particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces upon deformation. (a) Particle-laden interface in equilibrium, with the surface tension and the surface pressure generated by the particle monolayer being γ and Π . (b) Dilational deformation (left panel) characterized by surface dilational elasticity ε' and viscosity κ , and shear deformation (right panel) of particle-laden interface characterized by shear elasticity G' and viscosity η^s . (c) Out-of-plane deformations of particle-laden interfaces (from top to bottom): buckling (characterized by the bending elasticity κ^b), expulsion of material to the bulk and multilayer formation. Adapted from Garbin [230], Copyright (2019), with permission from Elsevier.

It is worth mentioning that the understanding of the interfacial rheological response of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces might be key for improving many technological applications of these systems, e.g. phase transfer catalysis, encapsulation, enhanced oil recovery or emulsification and foaming [238].

8.1. Response of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces to dilational stresses

Dilational rheology allows evaluating the modifications of the surface tension due to the change on the interfacial area accessible for the particle-laden monolayer. This can be defined in terms of the temporal evolution of the surface pressure $\delta\Pi(t)$ due to an uniaxial stress characterized by a modification on the interfacial area $\delta A(t)$ [239]

$$\delta\Pi(t) = \Pi(t) - \Pi_0 = \frac{\partial\Pi}{\partial A} \delta A = -\varepsilon(t)u(t), \quad (45)$$

with the time dependent dilational modulus being defined as

$$\varepsilon(t) = -A_0 \left(\frac{\partial\Pi}{\partial A} \right)_T. \quad (46)$$

Equation (44) defines a general time-dependent response function against a surface stress $\delta\Pi$ associated with a perturbation given by the compression strain

$$u(t) = \frac{\delta A}{A_0}. \quad (47)$$

For fluid films at equilibrium, it is possible to define the dynamic modulus by using the Gibbs elasticity ϱ

$$\varepsilon(t) \rightarrow \varepsilon_0 = \Gamma \left(\frac{\partial\Pi}{\partial\Gamma} \right)_{eq}, \quad (48)$$

with $\Gamma=1/A$ being the surface concentration. Assuming a oscillatory deformation of small-amplitude characterized by a frequency ω , the complex modulus can be defined as

$$\varepsilon(\omega) = \varepsilon'(\omega) + i\omega\kappa(\omega), \quad (49)$$

where the real part $\varepsilon'(\omega)$ corresponds to the storage modulus or surface dilational elasticity and the imaginary part $\varepsilon''(\omega)=\omega\kappa(\omega)$ is referred to the loss modulus, with κ being the surface dilational viscosity. This definition of the viscoelastic dilational modulus suggests the change on both the adsorption state of the particles at the fluid/fluid and the structure of the interface as result of the stress induced by the deformation. Therefore, it may be expected the emergence of different relaxation processes, with different characteristic time-scales, as response to any modification of the interfacial area [32, 240-243].

8.1.1 Dilational rheology of particle-laden interfaces.

Despite the experimental and theoretical efforts on understanding the response of particle-laden interfaces against dilational stresses, different aspects are far from clear. This is especially noticeable when theoretical predictions and experimental results are compared [32, 126, 162]. It should be noted that most of the studies related to the interfacial rheology of particle-laden interfaces have been limited to two types of particles: (i) silica, and (ii) polystyrene latex.

The dilational rheology of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces is governed by different parameters, including the wettability, interfacial coverage and particle anisotropy, which govern the inter-particle interactions and the microstructure of the interfacial film [21, 244, 245].

The seminal studies on the theoretical description of the interfacial rheology of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces were performed by Miller et al. [126]. They faced the analysis of the relaxation mechanisms emerging in particle-laden interfaces upon dilational stresses in terms of theoretical models derived from those commonly used for describing the dilational response of proteins and proteins-surfactant systems [113, 246]. Thus, it was possible to describe the dilational response of particle monolayers using the information contained in their adsorption isotherms. However, the applicability of the aforementioned model was not furtherly extended, mainly due to the necessity of obtaining many parameters, which in many cases are not easily accessible for particle-laden interfaces.

It was discussed above that the particle wettability presents a very critical impact on their attachment to the fluid/fluid interface, and hence it may be expected that the particle contact angle may affect very decisively to the dilational response of particle-laden interfaces. This was demonstrated by Safouane et al. [247] by studying the dilational response of fumed silica nanoparticle at the water/vapour interface by measuring the damping of capillary waves (frequency range 200 – 990 kHz). They found a strong correlation between the interfacial rheological response against dilation and the interfacial morphology, with the elastic component increasing with the hydrophobicity of the particles and the increase of the interfacial coverage, whereas the loss modulus remained rather independent of both parameters. Thus, the compressibility modulus for the more hydrophilic particles remains close to 0 (around 3 mN/m) whereas the increase of the particle hydrophobicity increase its value up to almost 200 mN/m. This rigidification of the interfacial film can be explained considering the densification of the particle-laden interface and the enhancement of the inter-particle interactions [248]. Furthermore, they found that independently of the degree of hydrophobization of the particles and the interfacial coverage, the elastic component

of the dilational response appears higher than the viscous one.

The works by Safouane et al. [247] were furtherly extended by Zang et al. [249]. They explored the low frequency range of the dilational response, and in particular the time-scales involved in such response. They found a relaxation process on a time-scale about 1000 s, which was ascribed to the reorganization of particles at the interface. This process was enhanced with the decrease of the particle hydrophobicity, which may be explained considering the decrease of the interfacial coverage, and the subsequent reduction of the steric hindrance within the interface. This leads to the enhancement of the mobility of the particles.

Kobayashi and Kawaguchi [250] explored the dilational response of latex particles spread at the water/vapour interface. They found that the behaviour of the monolayers was viscoelastic with independence of the strain rate, with both the storage and loss moduli increasing as the interfacial coverage increases up to a critical value of the coverage ($\Pi \sim 15$ mN/m). Once the threshold coverage is reached, both rheological parameters start to decrease steeply. This may be understood assuming that the dilational deformation induces a possible out-of-plane deformation of the particle-laden interface which distorts the 2D packing. The analysis of the frequency dependences of the viscoelastic parameters, i.e. storage and loss moduli, evidences the emergence of a transition from fluid-like to solid-like monolayers with the increase of the packing density. This agrees with the structural picture obtained from the studies by Bonales et al. [191]. It should be noted that it is very common to find that the rigidity for spread layers appears lower than for those obtained by compression. This may be probably related to the formation of non-equilibrium arrested states which introduce additional relaxation mechanism to the particle-laden interface [249, 251].

Del Rio et al. [252] deepened on the correlations existing between the interfacial organization and the rheological response, confirming the existence of a strong correlation between the type of phases appearing at the particle-laden interface and the dilational modulus. Furthermore, they found that the elastic component appears always higher than the viscous one for particle-laden interfaces in agreement with the results by Safouane et al. [247]. Thus, the storage modulus increases with the interfacial coverage within the low surface pressure range, whereas the loss modulus remains close to that of the water. This may be ascribed to the contribution of the inter-particle repulsive interactions with electrostatic origin. The increase of the interfacial density beyond a threshold value results in a sharp increase of the storage modulus up to reach a value around 350 mN/m. This is correlated to formation of a close-packed particle-laden interface as was observed by Brewster Angle Microscopy. It should be noted that in presence of a weak

electrostatic interaction, the storage modulus increases until 600 mN/m, which may be only explained assuming the existence of a reduced number of defects within the close-packed monolayer. As was found by Kobayashi and Kawaguchi [250], the storage and loss moduli drop at the highest value of the surface pressure as result of the emergence of out-of-plane deformations of the monolayer. It should be noted that the rheological response of latex monolayers was found qualitatively similar for both water/vapour and water/oil interfaces [188, 189].

Vella et al. [253] showed that the response of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces against dilational stresses can be also a matter of size. They studied monolayers of different monodisperse particles with the same chemical nature and found that the Young modulus appears inversely proportional to the dimension of the particles.

It is worth mentioning that in most of the cases the dilational flows induced under controlled laboratory conditions are always smaller than those expected under operational conditions in industry, which makes difficult to compare the experimental picture with real situation. This problem was addressed by Hilles et al. [254] for latex particles at the water/octane interface. They found that the linear region on the dilational response was circumscribed to deformation of very low strain.

8.1.2 Dilational rheology of monolayers of mixtures of colloidal particles and surfactants. It was discussed above that the modification of the wettability of particles by surfactant adsorption allows modulating the adsorption of particles at fluid/fluid interfaces. This has stimulated the study of the dilational rheology of monolayers formed by particle-surfactant mixtures [32, 47, 48]. The interaction of two oppositely charged components is frequently associated with the emergence of synergetic effects between both components on the interfacial properties [112, 127, 255-259]. However, this was not the case for mixtures of silica nanoparticles and CTAB as was evidenced from the study by Ravera et al. [47]. They analysed the dilational response at both water/oil and water/vapour interfaces in the low frequency limit (0.005 – 0.2Hz), and found a strong dependence of the viscoelastic response of particle-laden interfaces on the frequency. Furthermore, they observed higher elasticity values for particle-laden interfaces than for monolayers of pure surfactant. The latter is in agreement with the results by Tambe and Sharma [231] for mixtures of stearic acid and graphite particles at the water/decane interface. Furthermore, the effect of the formation of the particle-laden interface on the rheological properties was found stronger for the water/oil interface than for the water/vapor one. The extension of the rheological characterization for the aforementioned system to a larger frequency range (10^{-3} – 10^3 Hz) combining up to three different experimental techniques (oscillatory drops,

capillary pressure tensiometer and electrocapillary wave device) evidenced the presence of two different relaxation processes of the interface as response to the dilational stress. These were ascribed to: (i) diffusion-controlled adsorption of particles from the bulk to the interface, and (ii) reorganization of the adsorbed material at the interface [32, 48]. The first process governs the relaxation of the layer at low frequency, with the latter does the same at high frequency. These experimental results were well described using a rheological model combining a diffusion process and an arbitrary kinetics occurring within the interface. A detailed analysis of the rheological response of mixtures formed by CTAB and silica nanoparticles evidences that is controlled for an intricate balance of interactions which leads to the depletion of the CTAB from the solution to the particle surface. This results in a modulation of the the particle wettability and the inter-particle interactions in the bulk and at the interface [32, 33, 260].

The interfacial aging, characterized by an increase of the dilational elasticity and the formation of solid-like monolayers, also plays a very important role on the mechanical performance of the particle-laden interfaces against dilation [48, 188, 261, 262]. It should be noted that the rigidification of the interface with time occurs without any significant change of the surface tension. This suggests that particles are irreversibly attached to the fluid/fluid interface, and once the maximum coverage of the interface is reached, the exchange of particles between the bulk and the interface is negligible or present a very slow kinetics [261]. The elastic modulus for aged monolayers was found to be comparable with those reported for monolayers of latex particles [250, 252].

8.2. Response of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces to against shearing

The amplitude and time evolution of shear deformations are independent of those corresponding to any other mode, i.e. shear deformations are decoupled to the rest of interfacial modes [263, 264]. This allows one to give a definition for the shear elasticity corresponding to an in-plane deformation as the proportionality constant that relates the applied strain (u_{xy}) and the stress (σ_{xy}). Thus, for solid-like films it can be considered the existence of a Hookean behaviour characterized by: $\sigma_{xy}=Gu_{xy}$. On the other side, the description of the response of fluid-like films appears dominated by its viscous character, resulting in the following relationship

$$\sigma_{xy} = \eta^s \frac{du_{xy}}{dt}, \quad (50)$$

with du_{xy}/dt and η^s defining the strain rate and the interfacial shear viscosity, respectively. It should be noted that the existence of inter-particle interactions is expected to increase

the value of the viscoelastic parameters (G , η^S) because the energy applied for overcoming such interactions favours the flow of the surface elements. The complex shear modulus G^* can be defined for an oscillatory deformation as follows

$$G^*(\omega) = G'(\omega) + iG''(\omega) \equiv G' + i\omega\eta^S, \quad (51)$$

where G' and G'' represent the storage or shear elastic, and loss moduli, respectively. When the amplitude of the oscillatory deformations at fixed frequency ω is maintained small, the loss modulus can be defined in terms of the shear viscosity according to $G'' = \omega\eta^S$.

In current years, there is a strong interest on the understanding the response of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces against shear stresses due to its direct implication in many aspects involving these systems, e.g. foam and emulsion stabilization [162, 245, 265]. This has guided important research effort trying to understand the correlations existing between shear rheology and the morphology of the particle-laden interfaces, with the interactions between particles being the main driving force of such correlation [266]. This is important for the description of the response of particle-laden interface against shearing because the differences in the inter-particle interactions in bulk and at interface are on the bases of the differences on the shear response between particle-laden interfaces and their bulk counterparts [267].

8.2.1 Shearing particle-laden monolayers. Cicuta et al. [268] performed one of the first studies dealing with the characterization of the response of particle-laden interfaces against shearing. They studied polystyrene latex (3 μm of diameter) at the water/decane interface and found the opposite response against shear than against dilation. The shearing of polystyrene latex monolayers show a mainly viscous character of the monolayers with $G'' > G'$. This was different to the behaviour of β -lactoglobulin layers in which the behaviour appears governed by the elastic component. This can be understood considering that proteins can undergo deformation and compression as response to the shear deformation. Furthermore, the viscoelastic character of the particle-laden interface increases significantly when the surface coverage is above 75-80 % of the total interfacial area. This is explained by the emergence of jamming in the 2D film. The above behaviour appears similar to that reported by Yu et al. [269] for silica-laden interfaces. They found at low coverage, a viscous dominated response, which is reminiscent of a liquid-like structure. The increase of the coverage leads to an increase of both viscoelastic moduli at different rate, with the behaviour becoming elastic at the highest values of the coverage, i.e. solid-like. It should be noted that the transition between the viscous-like behaviour to the solid-like one is strongly dependent on the ionic strength. At low ionic strength, the particle-laden interface presents and almost negligible shear elasticity at low values

of the coverage, with the particles moving freely due to the repulsive interactions. At intermediate coverages, the elastic and viscous components become equivalent, leading to a strongly elastic behaviour at the highest values of the interfacial coverage. Similar dependences on the viscoelastic response were found with the increase of the ionic strength, with the value of the coverage for inducing the transition from a viscous-controlled response to an elastic-controlled one undergoing a reduction with the increase of the ionic strength. This was explained as result of the higher degree of particle aggregation emerging due to the screening of the repulsion between the charges on the particle surface.

The impact of the interfacial coverage on the shear response of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces was also explored by Imperiali et al. [270] using graphene oxide particles a model. They found that the freedom of the particles for the reorganization within the fluid/fluid interfaces presents a critical impact on the shear response, with the particle-laden interface behaving as a 2D-plasticized system at low fraction of coverage, whereas the behaviour becomes reminiscent of a perfect elastic interface for close-packed monolayers. This behaviour agrees with the reported by Barman and Christopher [271] for the response against shearing of polystyrene latex at the water/vapour interface, obtained using a double-wall interfacial rheometer coupled to a system enabling a visualization of the microstructure of the interfacial layer. They found that the increase of the interfacial coverage drives a transition from a shear thinning behaviour associated with the breakup of clusters of particles to a yielding one at the slip plane. This transition was justified by the modification of the mechanisms involved in the dissipation of the viscous stresses. However, yielding occur in this system well before the monolayer jamming, which provides evidences that the yielding or solid-like behaviour can appear before the close-packing or jamming of the particle-laden fluid/fluid interface. Furthermore, they found that the particle-laden interface can undergo significant shear induced ordering when the packing density is high. The results by Barman and Christopher [271] suggested that the mechanical response of particle-laden interface cannot be reduced to the emergence jammed or unjammed states within the interface. Furthermore, the increase of the interfacial coverage induces the emergence of a non-linear response on the particle-laden interface, with the dependence of the viscoelastic modulus on the surface coverage being governed by a power law [272]. Barman and Christopher [273] extended later their analysis of the shear response of particle-laden interfaces, and concluded that the viscoelastic character was defined by a constrain of the particle motion associated with both the inter-particle attraction due to the capillarity effects and the degree of caging induced by the local microstructure. Simultaneously, they found that elasticity and yield appear controlled by the

mesostructural organization of the local microstructure, with large domains of aligned hexagonal packed particles leading to elastic particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces as the domains start to break-up, whereas the formation of smaller domains results in an interfacial flow which leads to a viscous-like behaviour.

The understanding of the importance of the interfacial packing on the shear response was extended by Reynaert et al. [272]. They found that the formation of particle aggregates at the fluid/fluid interface results in a shear response that can be understood in terms of the same mechanism acting in bulk system. This provides a further confirmation of the important role of the inter-particle interactions in the control of the rheological as was furtherly confirmed using Brownian dynamic simulations by Wijmans and Dickinson [274]. The work by Beltramo et al. [245] provides further evidences on the importance of the interactions on the response of particle-laden interface against shearing. They found that the interfacial yield stress becomes more important as the strength of the lateral interactions increases. Furthermore, they found that the increase of the interfacial coverage from 0.47 to 0.88 leads to an increase of the elastic modulus and the yield stress by one order of magnitude. A detailed analysis of the dependence of the viscoelastic modulus on the interfacial coverage evidenced that this was almost negligible up to an interfacial coverage about 0.64, where it starts to grow with the viscous component being the dominating one. Then, at interfacial coverages in the range 0.75-0.80, the viscoelastic modulus reaches a plateau value associated with the interfacial jamming.

Another important aspect influencing the interfacial shear response is the anisotropy character of the particles as was demonstrated by Madivala et al. [275]. They studied monolayers of ellipsoidal polystyrene particles at both water/decane and water/vapour interfaces and found that the interfacial packing was mainly governed by the strength of the electrostatic interactions. Thus, monolayers at the water/decane interface show arrangements of individual particles coexisting with linear aggregates, whereas the formation of flower-like aggregates was found at the water/vapour interface. These differences on the organization of the particles at the interface result in different rheological response upon shearing, confirming that the interfacial morphology plays a central role on the mechanical response of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces. The detailed analysis of the rheological response of the ellipsoidal particles at the water/decane interface showed that it was governed by the elastic component of the shear component, with the viscoelastic modulus increasing with the interfacial modulus. It should be noted that the elastic modulus of the monolayers of ellipsoidal particles at fluid/fluid interfaces appears relatively high, even when the surface coverage remains low.

This later result combined with the dominance of the elastic component of the shear response is just the opposite situation to that reported for spherical particles by Cicuta et al. [268], which may be explained considering the existence of different mechanisms of interfacial relaxation [276]. Furthermore, monolayers of ellipsoidal particles present a buckling transition for high degrees of interfacial coverage, which does not occur when spherical particles are considered. Therefore, the differences on the rheological response of isotropic shaped particles and those with anisotropic shape against shearing may be justified in terms of the broad range of interfacial packings that can generate non-spherical particles depending on their degree of anisotropy. Thus, the different balance of interactions existing as function of the shape anisotropy of the particles can lead to different aggregation patterns at fluid/fluid interfaces and hence to different rheological responses on the particle-laden interfaces, e.g. the shear modulus of colloidal crystals formed by paramagnetic particles increase with the strength of the inter-particle repulsion [248].

Brown et al. [277] deepened on the study of the influence of the particle morphology on the shear response using non-spherical particles having different aspect ratio. They found a shear thickening phenomenon independently of the shape anisotropy of the particles. However, the anisotropy was reported as a critical parameter for inducing the jamming of the interfacial layer, the higher the anisotropy of the particles the lower the value of the threshold coverage for the onset on the formation of a jammed layer. Furthermore, the asymmetry of the particles can lead to the formation of kinetically trapped interfacial systems, which affects to the shear flows within the interface. This is correlated to the particle charge and the interfacial coverage [278, 279].

The roughness of the particles was also found a very important parameter on the control of the mechanical response of particle-laden interface against shearing [280], with the effect of the roughness being strongly correlated to the interfacial coverage of the fluid/fluid interface. This can be understood in terms of the inter-particle friction [277]. Thus, at low interfacial coverage, shear viscosity is reduced with the increase of the surface roughness, whereas the opposite is true as the monolayer jamming is closer [281]. This can be understood considering the role of the particle heterogeneity on the formation of particle-laden interfaces. Zanini et al. [282] showed that particles with high roughness may be trapped in metastable positions due to the pinning of the contact line, which may lead to a situation where hydrophilic particles behave as hydrophobic one and the latter as hydrophilic one. This enables the stabilization of water-in-oil and oil-in-water emulsions using a single type of particles without any modification of their wettability. The above discussion evidenced that the rheological response may be strongly influenced for the hydrophilic-hydrophobic

character of the particles. This was confirmed by Safouane et al. [247] for monolayers of fumed silica with different hydrophobicity degrees. They found that for the same degree of the interfacial coverage the increase of the particle hydrophobicity increases both the storage and the loss moduli, with the behaviour going from mainly elastic for particles with low hydrophobicity to purely viscous for highly hydrophobic particles. Furthermore, a gel point ($G' = G''$) was found for particles with intermediate wettability (contact angle around 90°). Zang et al. [30, 249, 283] extended the study of the effect of the hydrophobicity on the shear response of fumed silica monolayers. They do not found any dependence of the storage modulus on the strain amplitude for low values of the strain amplitude, with the storage modulus being almost two orders of magnitude higher than the lost modulus. Furthermore, they reported the existence of a melting transition for strain amplitudes above a threshold value (yield stress), which was characterized for a maximum on the loss modulus and the dropping of the storage modulus. For small deformations of low frequency, the particle-laden interface behaves mainly as a viscous material, whereas the opposite is true as the frequency is increased. This is reminiscent from that what happens in 3D soft solids, and can be explained in terms of a decrease of the characteristic time associated with the structural relaxation as result the increase of the strain-rate amplitude [284]. Similar reminiscence was also found in the quasi-linear dependence of the relaxation time on the shear rate. Similar behaviour to the above discussed was reported by Vandebriel et al. [285].

The time evolution of the response against shear of particle-laden interfaces can be also very interesting for the possible development of interface dominated systems. This was clear from the studies of the adsorption kinetics of silver nanoparticles (10–50 nm of diameter) to the water/toluene interface [286]. The result showed that both G' and G'' increase with time, which can be understood in terms of the densification of the particle-laden interface during the equilibration process. On the other side, the equilibrium films were found to be mainly elastic with a certain reminiscence of the behaviour of 2D glassy materials as evidenced the negative slope of the dependence of G'' on the deformation frequency. Furthermore, the shear response showed a strong dependence on the strain amplitude. The use of strain sweep measurements demonstrated the existence of shear thickening behaviour in G'' at large strain amplitudes, whereas G' did not shown any dependence on the strain amplitude until reaching the shear thickening point. The shear thickening may be accounted in terms of a power law with the values of the exponents for the storage and loss moduli being 2 and 1, respectively. The behaviour for gold nanoparticles at the water/vapour interface was found to be very different [287-290], having a gel-like behaviour characterized by a strain induced softening. Furthermore, no

dependences of the rheological response on the applied strain was found until overcoming a threshold value of about 0.1%. Once this threshold value is overcome, the storage modulus drops. The dependence of the viscoelastic moduli on the interfacial coverage is accounted for a power law with an exponent around 0.65, which can be considered reminiscent of the behaviour of a percolating system [240, 291, 292].

8.2.2 Shearing monolayers of mixtures of particles and surfactants. The study of the response against shear stresses of monolayers formed by mixtures of particles and surfactants at fluid/fluid interfaces has received less attention than their counterparts formed only particles. Maestro et al. [284] evidenced by using strain-sweep shear experiments that silica nanoparticles decorated with CTAB trapped at the water/vapour interface present a behaviour of 2D solid with amorphous order, with its shear modulus appearing in the range 0.1-1 N/m. These values are similar to that reported for silica-laden interfaces [249, 283]. A detailed analysis of the rheological behaviour of monolayers of silica nanoparticles decorated with CTAB shows that at low frequency the shear modulus follows a power-law dependence on the interfacial coverage. This is similar to that found in systems undergoing a gelling transition, with the shear modulus being negligible below a critical value of the interfacial density, Γ_c , and growing sharply as the system is closer to the close-packing

$$G' \sim \left(\frac{\Gamma}{\Gamma_c} - 1 \right)^\beta. \quad (52)$$

The solid-like interface formed by CTAB-decorated silica nanoparticles was found to deform under a shear strain ramp beyond a yielding point, inducing a plastic flow [285]. This yielding point is strongly dependent on the interfacial coverage and follows a power law $\tau^* \sim \Gamma^\alpha$ (with τ^* being the yield stress). This behaviour is accounted for a model in which all the particle-level and many-body physics are considered: non-affine displacements, local connectivity, and their evolutions in terms of cage-breaking and inter-particle interactions mediated by the particle chemistry and colloidal forces.

Mass et al. [293] analysed using shear rheology the interfacial interaction of lipids and silica particles with different degrees of hydrophobicity at the water/oil interface, and found a two-step adsorption kinetics, with the first step having a characteristic time of around 1 hour. This step is characterized by the increase of G' as result of the formation of an elastic interfacial layer with high inter-particle cohesion, whereas the second step is extended along a larger time-scale and is characterized by a slow increase of both G' and G'' due to the accumulation of material at the interface. This process continues until the steady state is reached. It should be noted that the values of the storage and loss moduli of the layers were found several orders of magnitude higher

than those corresponding to monolayers of pure surfactant, which agrees with the results reported in other studies [247, 294, 295].

8.3. Out of plane deformations

The application of sufficiently large compression stress to a particle-laden interface may lead to elastic instabilities, which are reflected in out-of-plane deformations of the particle layer [230, 296, 297]. The emergence of these processes may be understood considering the phenomena emerging on particle-laden interfaces as are compressed. The initial compression of a particle-laden interface can result in the formation of a close-packed film, even for interfacial jamming states. Further compression of the interface can induce out-of-plane deformations which may result in buckling, expulsion of material from the interface to the bulk or multilayer formation [298].

The condition for the buckling of the particle-laden interface is that the surface pressure assumes a value high enough to make dropping the effective surface tension of the interface down to a quasi-null value. However, under some specific conditions the expulsion of particles from the monolayers is favoured in relation to the buckling phenomena. This can be understood by comparison the energy associated with the trapping of a particle ΔE_p , and the mechanical work $dW = \Pi dA$ associated with the compression of the interface. Thus, the expulsion occurs only when the trapping energy is overcome by the mechanical work of the compression, and hence the boundary condition for inducing the expulsion of particles is defined as $dW = \Delta E_p$. Thus, taking the dA as the cross-sectional area of the particle, it is possible to define the balance for particle expulsion as [17]

$$\Pi = \gamma_{12}(1 \pm \cos \theta)^2. \quad (53)$$

The above expression does not account for the presence of interactions. Attractive inter-particle interactions lead to the formation of solid-like films with elastic behaviour, in which the expulsion upon compression is completely hindered [43].

Leahy et al. [299] studied the compression of monolayers of gold nanoparticles capped with dodecanethiol beyond the close-packing, and found the formation of local folds and then a transition to the formation of multilayers, with the wavelength of the wrinkles providing information of the bending modulus of monolayers and multilayers making use of the elasticity theory. Vella et al. [253] found that the wrinkling of the particle-laden interface emerges once particles cluster together. This suggests that the particle-laden interface behaves as a solid film upon compression beyond the monolayer collapse, with the characteristic length of the buckling being defined as

$$\lambda = \pi \left[\frac{4}{3(1-\mathcal{G})(1-\nu_p)} \right]^{1/4} \sqrt{2Rl_c}, \quad (54)$$

with ν_p being the Poisson ratio. The predictions of the above model works reasonably well for particles with a diameter above 1 μm . However, deviations are found for nano-sized colloids, with the buckling wavelength being underestimated. This is an indication of a high bending elasticity, κ^b [300]. Monolayers formed for particles with anisotropic shape can release compressive stress by an interfacial rearrangement. This results in a flipping transition when they are compressed. Further compression can lead to the expulsion of particle to the adjacent fluid phase [276].

Razavi et al. [301] showed that the phenomena occurring in particle-laden interfaces upon collapse can be controlled by the particle wetting. This is ascribed to the role of the inter-particle interactions on the interfacial structure and the response to deformations. Thus, particles with low hydrophobicity lead to the formation of fluid-like monolayers, which collapse irreversibly with particle expulsion toward the bulk. The increase of the hydrophobicity of the particles leads to a solid-like films with strong cohesive interactions. These films present a high compressional elasticity, which favors a reversible collapse through monolayer wrinkling and folding. These results evidence that the attractive inter-particle interactions arrest the stress relaxation through particle expulsion to the bulk.

9. Aspects to consider on the study of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces

The above discussion has provides a general perspective on the behavior of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces. However, this is a rapid evolving field, in which the specific characteristic of the particles can lead to the emergence of a broad range of interfacial behaviors and properties. Therefore, for a whole understanding of the physico-chemical behavior of particle laden fluid/fluid interfaces is necessary to present a brief perspective on some important aspects for the control of the interfacial organization and properties of the particle layers. However, a detailed analysis of these aspects appears out of the scope of the present review.

9.1. Hard vs. soft colloids

It is true that the softness of the particles does not avoid its adsorption to fluid/fluid interfaces. However, the competition between the bulk elasticity and surface tension in soft particles results in their stretching at the fluid/fluid interface, which increases the energy associated with the particle trapping at the interface [133, 163, 302-304]. On the other side, the direct interactions between particles are reduced

with the increase of the particle deformability, whereas the capillary attractions appear strengthen [305]. Furthermore, the deformability of soft particles leads to the emergence of interesting interfacial mesostructures, which plays a very important role on the stabilization of dispersed systems, mainly emulsions [306-309].

9.2. Particle dimensions and shape

As was discussed above, the trapping energy of particles at a fluid/fluid interfaces is strongly dependent on the particle size. This determines the ability of particle to remain trapped at the interface and their ability for stabilizing emulsions and foams [310, 311]. On the other side, non-spherical particles can lead to the formation of unique self-assembled structures as result of the capillary interactions. Furthermore, the control of the anisotropy of the particles may allow tuning the stability of emulsions and control the rheological response of the interfaces [24, 275, 312, 313].

9.3. Particle surface chemistry and charge density

The specific chemistry of the particle surface is expected to influence strongly the wettability of particles trapped at fluid/fluid interfaces [20, 59, 314], and as matter of fact modifies the energetic landscape and organization of particles at the fluid/fluid interface [315-317]. In particular, chemical heterogeneities on the particle can lead to the undulation of the contact line. On the other side, the surface charge of the particles governs the electrostatic and capillary interactions. Furthermore, the charge heterogeneities can modify significantly the interaction balance, and hence the organization of particles at fluid/fluid interfaces appears much influenced by the surface charge of the particles [318, 319].

9.4. Passive vs. Active colloids

The term colloid is commonly used for defining passive colloids, in which the adsorption at the fluid/fluid interface results in a reduction of the free energy of the system. Furthermore, they present rheological and dynamic behaviours, which are closely correlated to the thermodynamics description of the system. On the other side, the term active colloids accounts for a type of self-propelled colloidal object in which the interactions occur only through short-range repulsion forces. These colloids presents motions and dynamics assemblies, which can occur by harnessing energy from the environment [13, 162, 320, 321]. Active colloids can find at fluid/fluid interfaces a very interesting environment, where the capillary interaction can be modulated by the action of external fields to tune their motion, interactions or assembly [322, 323].

9.5. Homogeneous vs. Janus particles.

Homogeneous particles are commonly trapped at the fluid/fluid interface in such a way that appears independent on the particle position and orientation [118]. This is not true for Janus particle, which are generally amphiphilic. This may define an enhanced adsorption at the fluid/fluid interface to minimize the unfavourable contacts with one of the fluid phases [324]. Therefore, the adsorption of Janus particles appears much stronger than that of homogeneous particles, which has stimulated their use on the stabilization of emulsions [21, 325].

9.6. Type of fluid/fluid interface

Fluid/fluid interfaces include two type of systems: (i) liquid/gas interface, and (ii) liquid/liquid interfaces. The differences of the chemical nature of the phases defining the interface may influence the formation of particle-laden systems. Thus, for liquid/gas interfaces, the particle wettability is the main driving force guiding the assembly. Furthermore, the role of the dielectric constant of the liquid phase cannot be neglected when charged colloids are considered, with the properties of the gas phase playing a minor role on the assembly of the particle layer [275]. On the other side, for liquid/liquid interfaces, the partition of the particles between both liquids defines the equilibrium contact angle. Furthermore, for liquid/liquid interfaces, the difference between the dielectric constants of the two liquids influences the balance of interactions, and as matter of fact the particle organization at the interface [78, 120]. It should be noted that most of the studied reporting particle-laden liquid/liquid interfaces are focused in systems formed for an aqueous phase and an oil phase. However, in recent years it is growing the interest for understanding most complex oil/oil interfaces [1, 19].

10. Beyond the physico-chemistry: A brief perspective to the potential applications of particle-laden interfaces on the stabilization of dispersed systems

The above discussion has been focused so far on the description of the main physico-chemical bases describing the behaviour of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces. However, the advances on the understanding of the behaviour of these systems has stimulated an extensive research activity focused on exploiting the ability of auto-organization and self-assembly of colloidal particles at fluid/fluid interfaces for designing a broad range of soft interface dominated materials. There are currently many examples of promising materials based on particle-laden interface and an exhaustive discussion about them is out the scope of this review. In this section, the impact of particles on the stabilization of dispersed systems, mainly emulsions and foams, is discussed. For a deeper understanding of the potential applications of particle-laden interface from a most

nanotechnological perspective, the reading of references [23, 114, 316, 326-329] is recommendable.

The understanding of the interfacial properties of particle-laden interfaces play a very important role on the control of the stability and properties of dispersed systems, including foams, emulsions and thin films, which it is currently important because the widespread application of dispersed systems in food products, cosmetics, wastewater treatment, or oil recovery/treatment [75, 330-336]. The importance of particle layers on the stabilization of emulsions and foams can be understood considering their long-term stability and their novel rheological properties. The long-term stability arises from the difficulties associated with the reduction of the interfacial area once the particles are quasi-irreversibly attached to the fluid/fluid interface. Furthermore, particle-laden interfaces can provide an additional mechanism for hindering, at least partially, the destabilization processes of emulsions and foams, e.g. creaming (or sedimentation), flocculation, coalescence, and Ostwald ripening [1, 337-340], due to the formation of a protective shell on the external surface of the droplets or bubbles which provides them with a mechanical protection [1, 337-340]. Therefore, the stabilization and properties of dispersed systems appear closely correlated to the interfacial and mechanical properties of single interfaces, with the adsorbed particle layer enabling the dampening of the external perturbations to avoid the destabilization of the dispersed systems and its rupture [17, 75, 341].

Different authors have reported the importance of the coverage of the particle-laden interface on its ability for ensuring the stabilization of emulsions and foams [278, 342, 343]. This may be understood considering that the steric hindrance associated with the formation of a dense particle layer may contribute to the mechanical stability of emulsions and foams, which agrees with the results by Stratford et al. [344] and Maestro et al. [45]. They demonstrated the high efficiency of jammed particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces for the stabilization of dispersed systems. Therefore, as was stated by Frith et al. [345], the formation of a close-packed particle layer provides enough rigidity to the droplets and bubbles, which is favorable for the stability. This can be understood considering that a process such as the jamming can drive to the interface to an arrested state, which can minimize the interfacial tension driven coarsening, and as matter of fact increases the interfacial stabilization. Several authors have explored the correlations existing between the interfacial properties of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces and the stabilization of dispersed systems [45, 334, 346-348]. It is commonly assumed that the formation of a sufficiently dense particle-laden fluid/fluid interface can be considered as a main driving force for the stability of dispersed systems. This can be explained considering the effect of the particle coverage on the rheological response of the interface. At high

coverage, it may be expected a viscoelastic behaviour, with the elastic contribution being very high due to the inter-particle interactions. Therefore, it may be expected that the rheological performance of particle-laden interfaces may play a very central role on the stabilization process of dispersed systems, mainly by its importance on the control of the film thinning [349]. This is evidenced from the studies by Sullivan and Kilpatrick [350], in which the better stabilization of foams and emulsions was found for rigid and stagnant particle films. These results suggest that the inter-particle interactions should play a non-negligible role on the stabilization of foams and emulsions because the formation of particle bridges can enhance their stability, especially at low values of the interfacial coverage. This can be understood considering that the aggregation of droplets and bubbles can result in stable flocs, with these close interfaces leading to the formation of particle-zips which result in networked monolayers contributing to the stabilization process [343, 351, 352]. Therefore, the above picture shows clearly that the particle-laden fluid/fluid interface contributes to prevent the coalescence of droplets and bubbles, which enhances the stability of emulsions and foams.

The stability against drainage of foams can be partially improved by the increase of both shear viscosity and the dilational modulus [279]. Cervantes-Martínez et al. [346] showed that particle layers having a high resistance upon compression provide stability to foams by minimizing the shrinking of small bubbles. This was demonstrated by using the Gibbs criterion, which enables the establishment of a condition for the stabilization of dispersed systems in terms of a relationship between the surface tension and the dilational elasticity. This criterion suggests that only particle-laden interfaces fulfilling $\varepsilon' > \gamma/2$, can lead to stable foams or emulsions [347]. However, as was shown by Stocco et al. [347], the Gibbs criterion is only applicable for emulsions and foams containing spherical droplets or bubbles. Furthermore, Stocco et al. [347] showed that gel-like particle layers provide a better stabilization of the dispersed systems in agreement with the above discussed role of the interfacial jamming. However, the role of the rheological properties on the stabilization of dispersed systems is far from clear. Santini et al. [7, 49, 52, 53] showed that carbon particles can lead to the formation of stable foams and emulsions, without a clear dependence of their stability and the rheological response of the interface. This controversy is also supported by the results obtained for the stabilization of foams and emulsions using mixtures of silica nanoparticles and palmitic acid [50, 51], with the stabilization of foams using silica nanoparticles decorated with palmitic acid being not possible, even though the dilational viscoelastic modulus assumed very high values (> 100 mN/m) [51]. On the other side, emulsions were stabilized without any significant

correlation between the stabilization process and the rheological properties of the water/hexane [50].

The above discussion included so far an analysis of the role of the dilational modulus on the stabilization of dispersed systems. However, the influence of the shear modulus cannot be neglected due to its correlation with the interfacial structure and coverage, with the formation of gel-like layers being essential for ensuring a good stabilization of the dispersed systems [275, 285, 353]. This was demonstrated by Brugger et al. [306] using poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) particles for the stabilization of emulsions. They found that elastic interfaces are suitable for emulsion stabilization, whereas the opposite is true for viscous interfaces (high G'' values). This agrees with the results by Harbottle et al. [354]. They found for emulsions stabilized by asphaltene that a viscous dominant interfacial microstructure leads to a fast coalescence (on the order of seconds) between two droplets in intimate contact, whereas no coalescence signature were found for droplets coated with particles layers having a microstructure dominated by the elastic compounds. This transition between coalescing and no coalescing droplets was related to a high shear yield stress ($\sim 10^4$ Pa), which depends on the film shear yield point and the film thickness, with the increase of the elastic stiffness preventing the mobility and rupture of the particle layer. Therefore, it can be expected that a solid-like film can provide an energy barrier against coalescence.

Another important aspect for the stabilization of foams and emulsions by particle-layers is the control of the morphology and droplet size distribution. These aspects are governed by the particle size and their contact angle at the fluid/fluid interfaces, with the stabilization making necessary a partial wettability of the particles for both phases. Thus, for particles trapped at a fluid/fluid interface, it will be possible to find two different cases. For relatively hydrophilic particles ($\theta < 90^\circ$), it would be expected the formation of oil(air)/water dispersions for mixtures containing equal volumes of both fluid phase, whereas the opposite situation is commonly found for hydrophobic particles ($\theta > 90^\circ$). This allows defining that the inversion point appears at $\theta = 90^\circ$, i.e. for particles with the same affinity for both fluids [75]. It should be noted that the addition of surfactant can help on the control of the stability of emulsions and foams because they can modify the ability of particles to remain trapped at the fluid/fluid interface [231]. This is clear from the work by Binks et al. [60], in which the stabilization of emulsions by silica nanoparticles decorated with a bicatenary cationic surfactant was explored. They found that the addition of a certain concentration of surfactant allows inducing the transition between different types of emulsions, which is explained from the different degree of hydrophobization of the nanoparticles. This is related to the change of the contact angle of the particles at the fluid/fluid interface, existing a

correlation between the addition of surfactant, the degree of hydrophobicity of the particles and the type of emulsion obtained. Thus, at for low surfactant concentrations, particles remain hydrophilic with contact angle lower than 90° stabilizing oil in water (o/w) emulsions, whereas for intermediate surfactant concentrations the particle hydrophobicity is enhanced ($\theta > 90^\circ$) which results in the formation of water in oil emulsions (w/o). For the highest surfactant concentrations, particles become hydrophilic again and the contact angle drops below 90° , which drives again the formation of o/w again [355]. Similar results have been also found for chemically modified particles [356]. The change of the particle wettability does not affect only to the stabilization of emulsions and can be also exploited for foam stabilization [357-359]. However, there are no studies dealing with the use of surfactants to tune the particle hydrophobicity for enabling a transition from aqueous foams to free aqueous drops surrounded by a particle shell, e.g. dry water or liquid marbles. However, this type of structures has been obtained by using hydrophobic particles [360, 361]. Figure 11 shows an idealized picture of the correlations between the contact angle and the curvature of the interface in relation to a water/vapour interface.

Figure 11. (a) Particle position at the water/vapour interface as a function of the wettability. (b) Bending behaviour of the particle-laden fluid/fluid interface as function of the particle wettability. Reprinted from Yu et al. [362], Copyright (2021), with permission from Elsevier.

The non-uniform wetting of the particles, i.e. the meniscus formed by the contact angle, can also modify the energetic landscape of the interface and consequently the ability of particles for stabilizing dispersed systems [44, 155, 281]. Ally et al. [363] reported the role of the particle adhesion at the fluid/fluid interface on the particle wettability and geometry of the contact line. Furthermore, the gravitational effects can result to meniscus deformation for big particles, which may be an additional source of instability [364].

The stability provided by particle layers to foams and emulsions allows using this type of materials as templates for the production of porous materials, e.g. solid foams. This can

be done by drying and sintering the wet system, or by direct solidification of the bulk liquid phase [358, 362, 365]. Gonzenbach et al. [359, 366] used this concept on the fabrication of solid foams using liquid foams stabilized by mixtures of particles and different short length surfactant as precursors. Zabiegaj et al. [6, 7, 367, 368] followed a similar approach on the preparation of particle stabilized solid foams using carbonaceous and alumina particles.

Beyond the stabilization of dispersed systems, particle-laden interfaces can find many other applications. An example is the exploitation of colloidal particles at the water/vapour interface for mitigating or totally suppressing the coffee-ring effect in evaporating sessile droplets [369, 370]. This is possible because during the evaporation process appears different process simultaneously to the evaporation itself: adsorption at the fluid/fluid interface and adsorption at the solid/fluid interface [371]. The modulation of the properties of the particles contained in the evaporating suspension allows controlling their trapping at the fluid/fluid interface and their adsorption at the solid/fluid one, which influence on the morphology of the deposition pattern. Therefore, the final deposit is the result of a complex balance between up to three different types of interactions: particle–particle, particle–fluid/fluid interface, and particle–substrate [372].

11. Concluding Remarks

The ubiquity of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces in different aspects with impact in the quality of life of modern society has stimulated the interest of both academia and industry for unravelling the main physico-chemical forces driving the assembly of a broad range of colloidal micro- and nano-particles at interfaces between two fluids of different nature. This is essential for exploiting the versatility of particle-laden fluid layers as a platform for the fabrication of different types of interface dominated systems, ranging from classical particle-stabilized foams and emulsions (Pickering and bijels) to more sophisticated reconfigurable devices. This is only possible from a careful examination of the main aspects that govern the assembly of the particles at the fluid/fluid interface, mainly the particle wettability, which can be evaluated in terms of the contact angle of the particle at the interface, and the inter-particle interactions. This makes necessary a careful examination of the impact of the above mentioned parameters on the organization the particles and their dynamics at the interface, as well as on the relaxation mechanisms of the interfaces upon a mechanical stress, and how such physico-chemical aspects can be modulated by chemical or physical methods. This makes possible to exploit the behaviour of particle-laden Interfaces for opening interesting avenues for nanoscience and nanotechnology.

It is true that this review has paid mainly attention to the most simple case (chemically isotropic hard spherical colloids), disregarding aspects such as the anisotropy in chemistry or size and the deformability of the colloids, which may present a critical role on the assembly of the particles at the fluid/fluid interface and the properties of the particle-laden layers. Nevertheless, the broad perspective used for the analysis of the mechanistic bases and consequences of the trapping of particles at fluid/fluid interfaces makes of this review an excellent guide for both researchers and technologist facing for first time this type of systems or for experimented one trying to exploit the whole potential of particle-laden fluid/fluid interfaces.

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